

CRISTAL

CLIMATE RESILIENT AND ENVIRONMENTALLY
SUSTAINABLE TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE,
WITH A FOCUS ON INLAND WATERWAYS

D7.1 - RP specification and Baseline measurements.

RP Specification and Baseline measurements including action plan to equip IWW with cold-ironing facilities

CRISTAL - Climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport infrastructure, with a focus on inland waterways

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation/Term	Description
AGN	Agreement on Main Inland Waterways of International importance
AIPO	Agenzia Interregionale per il fiume Po
CEF	Connecting Europe Facility
CEMT	“Conférence Européenne des Ministres des Transports” – referring to a classification of European Inland Waterways created by the European Conference of European Ministers of Transport
CI	Cold Ironing
CNIT	“Conto Nazionale Infrastrutture e Trasporti” – National Infrastructure and Transport Account published by the Italian Ministry of Infrastructures and Transport

CNC	Core Network Corridors of the TEN-T
DEWS	Flood and Drought Early Warning System
DT	Digital Twin
EnoLL	European Network of Living Labs
EPRS	Directorate-General for European Parliamentary Research Service
EC	Electric Charge
EU	European Union
FEWS	Flood Early Warning System
FOS	Fiber Optic Sensor Technology
GA	Grant Agreement
GSE	“Gestore dei Servizi Energetici” - Italian Energy Services Operator
ISPRA	Istituto superiore per la protezione e la ricerca ambientale, the Italian Institute for Environmental Protection and Research
IV	Infrastrutture Venete S.r.l.
IWT	Inland Waterway trTransport
IWW	Inland WaterWay
KET	Key enabling technologies
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LL	Living Lab
LNG	Liquid Natural Gas
LV	Low Voltage
ML	Machine Learning
MV	Medium Voltage
NST	"Nomenclature uniforme des marchandises pour les Statistiques de Transport" – a European standard designed to categorize goods for transport statistics.
OPS	On Power Supply
RIS	River Information Services
SCMS	Syncro-modal Corridor Management System
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SHM	Structural Health Monitoring
SSP	Shore-to-ship power
TEN-T	Trans-European Transport Network
tkm	Tonne-kilometres

TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UN	United Nations
VNF	Voies Navigables de France
WP	Work Package

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Table of contents

Document summary information	2
Revision history	3
List of abbreviations	3
1. Executive Summary.....	8
1.1. Introduction	8
1.2. Mapping CRISTAL outputs	9
1.3. Deliverable Overview and Report Structure	12
2. Italian River Pilot scenario.....	14
2.1. Pilot Case IWW infrastructure scenario.....	14
2.1.1. “Padano-Veneto” inland waterway system.....	14
2.1.2. Cremona-Mantua-Po River mouth (infrastructure operator: AIPo)	17
2.1.3. Fissero – Tartaro – Canalbianco – Po di Levante and Po-Brondolo canals (infrastructure operator: Infrastrutture Venete)	18
2.2. “Padano-Veneto” inland waterway infrastructure: governance	19
2.3. Traffic flows.....	20
2.4. Stakeholders.....	23
2.5. SWOT analysis	28
3. Pilot specification.....	30
3.1. Tools/systems addressed in the Italian River Pilot.....	30
3.1.1. Tools/systems to improve the reliability of the IWW	30
3.1.1.1. Navigability conditions prediction model.....	31
3.1.1.2. Smart bulletin.....	32
3.1.1.3. DT (developed in WP5)	33
3.1.1.4. SCMS (developed in WP3)	33
3.1.2. Tools/systems to improve the sustainability of the IWW	34
3.1.2.1. Cold ironing.....	34
3.1.2.2. GAP analysis	35
3.1.3. Tools/systems for a preventive maintenance	35
3.1.3.1. Acoustic emissions SHM	35
3.1.3.2. Fiber Optic Sensor System	36
3.2. Po River Living Lab.....	36
4. Pilot execution plan	39
4.1. Tools/systems developed in WP7 (Italian pilot).....	39
4.1.1. Prediction model.....	39
4.1.2. Smart bulletin.....	41

4.1.3.	Cold ironing feasibility study.....	41
4.1.4.	GAP analysis	43
4.2.	Tools/systems developed in other WPs based on the Italian pilot situation.....	44
4.2.1.	DT (developed in WP5)	44
4.2.2.	SCMS (developed in WP3)	45
4.2.3.	Acoustic emissions SHM (developed in WP2 and WP5)	45
4.2.4.	Fiber Optic Sensors system (developed in WP2)	46
4.3.	Italian pilot Living Lab.....	47
5.	Expected Pilot Results & Assessment Plan	52
5.1.	Expected project key results which are related to the subject matter of the pilot	52
5.1.1.	KPI's of the Italian Pilot	52
5.2.	Assessment plan.....	54
5.2.1.	Innovation plan and expected impact of CRISTAL at the regional and EU level.....	54
6.	Focusing on Cold ironing – Opportunities, needs and governance framework	58
6.1.	Cold ironing an innovation application for sustainable river ports areas	58
6.2.	Best practices at the European level	60
6.3.	Minimum standards for Cold Ironing in relation to inland navigation systems	67
6.4.	Governance & Stakeholders involvement.....	69
6.4.1.	Stakeholders interviews – summary and key takeaways.....	69
6.5.	Mapping and identification of existing landing points	70
7.	Cold ironing development strategy	72
7.1.	Long-term vision and strategy	72
7.2.	Scenario hypotheses	73
7.3.	Assessing the feasibility from the technical and economical viewpoints	74
7.3.1.	Focus on environmental impacts.....	74
8.	Cold Ironing Action Plan and recommendations	77
8.1.	The Action Plan approach.....	77
8.2.	Steps of implementation of the Action Plan	78
8.3.	Recommendations for a Monitoring Plan and Communication activities	80
8.4.	Input for designing typologies of cold-ironing interventions	80
9.	Conclusions.....	83
10.	References	84
11.	List of tables.....	85
12.	List of figures.....	85

1. Executive Summary

The "RP specification and Baseline measurements" report offers a comprehensive examination of the development perspective of the Italian River pilot in general together with a specific focus on the cold-ironing solution with particular reference to key Inland Waterways in Italy, while outlining strategies for innovation implementation and assessment.

To this end, the different characteristics of the Italian waterway system are recalled, with particular reference to the Po River from Cremona to the mouth in the Adriatic Sea and the canals Fissero-Tartaro-Canalbianco-Po di Levante and Po-Brondolo, also linking to the Venice Lagoon. Moreover, a brief description of the governance framework and, in particular, of the stakeholders being involved in the pilot.

Within this context, the Italian pilot aims to improve asset management and promote the navigability of the Italian inland waterways' infrastructure, using new technologies and considering green and environmental impacts and improvement of the resilience.

In this regard, the report provides further details on the Pilot specification, explaining its objectives and how it is linked to the rest of the project. This is followed by the description of the execution plan and the expected outputs and results.

Moreover, the report focuses on providing RP Specification and Baseline measurements including action plan to equip IWW with cold-ironing facilities. This innovative approach, often referred to as cold ironing/shore connection, shore-to-ship power (SSP), is being widely developed starting from maritime ports. In our study, instead, we are particularly focusing on inland waterways (where demand for power supply is characterised by lower values in terms of voltage, etc.). Moreover, this initiative is synergic with other environmentally friendly developments such as electric propulsion (with batteries to be recharged as well) and the search for renewable energy production, possibly on-site.

1.1. Introduction

This deliverable has been developed for the CRISTAL project. Its aim is to detail the Padano-Veneto IWW scenario, to illustrate the objectives of Italian River Pilot, to explain the execution plan with the baseline measurements and the expected results.

Italian River Pilot has three main objectives: to increase the reliability of the IWW, to improve the sustainability and finally to make the preventive maintenance of locks and the riverbed more effective. All the objectives are linked to the CRISTAL global objectives which are to improve the reliability of IWW transportation and increase its share in the different transport modes.

To achieve the first objective, a navigability conditions prediction model and a smart bulletin will be directly developed in the pilot while some use-cases of the Digital Twin (DT) and some features of Syncromodal Corridor Management System (SCMS) will be customized, respectively by WP5 and WP3, on the basis of the Italian IWW.

As far as the sustainability objective is concerned, a feasibility study for the implementation of cold ironing systems in the quays along the Fissero-Tartaro-Canalbianco-Po di Levante will be developed. Moreover, a GAP analysis of the compliance with the climate change mitigation and adaptation international standards and EU policy of the organizational model of some IWW stakeholders will be carried out.

The last objective related to predictive maintenance will be achieved through an initial evaluation of the effectiveness of acoustic emission technology for assessing the good condition of a lock (see WP5) and with the development of a prototype of a fiber optic sensor system to monitor the accumulation of debris on the riverbed (see WP2).

1.2. Mapping CRISTAL outputs

Table 1 Alignment of D7.1 contents to the corresponding GA deliverable & task(s) descriptions

CRISTAL GA Component Title	CRISTAL GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D7.1 RP specification and Baseline measurements.	<i>RP Specification and Baseline measurements</i>	<p><i>Chapter 2 Italian River Pilot Baseline situation and objectives</i></p> <p><i>Chapter 3. Pilot specification</i></p> <p><i>Chapter 4. Pilot Execution Plan</i></p> <p><i>Chapter 5. Pilot Results & Assessment Plan: the Baseline values</i></p>	<p><i>Starting from the in-depth analysis of the current situation of the key aspects of the Italian river pilot (in coordination and continuity with D6.1) a step further is made with particular reference to the pilot specification and the provision of baseline data. In particular, baseline data provides the reference value according to the initial situation, with reference to tests and studies being carried out in the Italian River Pilot.</i></p>
	<i>Action plan to equip IWW with cold-ironing facilities</i>	<p><i>Chapter 6. Focusing on Cold ironing – Opportunities, needs and governance framework</i></p> <p><i>Chapter 7. Cold ironing development strategy</i></p>	<p><i>This section offers a comprehensive examination of the development perspective of the cold-ironing solution with particular reference to key Inland Waterways in Italy. To this end, opportunities and needs are analysed as to provide a thorough</i></p>

		<p><i>Chapter 8. Cold Ironing Action Plan and recommendations</i></p>	<p><i>assessment of the feasibility of a proposed development strategy and implementation plan.</i></p> <p><i>As a key outcome, an action plan is outlined according to a comprehensive and strategic perspective addressing not only the IWT landscape but also such relevant synergic aspects as sustainable mobility and tourism as well as the transition to renewable energies with the spread of electric propulsion also in waterborne transport.</i></p>
TASKS			
<p>Task 7.1 Pilot supervision, concept assessment and coordination with WP6</p>	<p><i>On the basis of the scenario set in WP1, the solutions proposed by WP2, WP3, WP5 and the input from WP6, the set of technologies and system to be tested in the Po River pilot will be identified with the related monitoring technique and KPI.</i></p>	<p><i>Chapter 2 Italian River Pilot Baseline situation and objectives</i></p> <p><i>Chapter 3. Pilot specification</i></p> <p><i>Chapter 4. Pilot Execution Plan</i></p> <p><i>Chapter 5. Pilot Results & Assessment Plan: the Baseline values</i></p>	<p><i>These chapters are further elaborating and updating the analysis of the corridor under examination carried out in WP6 (namely, D6.1). In particular, a step further is made with reference to the pilot specification and the provision of baseline data.</i></p>
<p>Task 7.2 Engineering and implementation: New forecasting navigability model and green port cold ironing</p>	<p><i>This task is addressing:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>• The realisation of a prediction model for Po river navigability conditions</i> <i>• study for the realization of a network of cold iron facilities along the Fissero – Tartaro –</i> 	<p><i>Chapter 2 Italian River Pilot Baseline situation and objectives</i></p> <p><i>Chapter 3. Pilot specification</i></p> <p><i>Chapter 4. Pilot Execution Plan</i></p>	<p><i>A general overview and update is provided by chapters 2-5 with reference to different tools and technologies. Moreover, concerning chapters 6-8, it is to highlight the particular focus on cold ironing. In this regard, starting from a comprehensive examination of the development</i></p>

	<p><i>Canalbianco – Po di Levante e Po – Brondolo channel including a dedicated designing model guidelines and a related masterplan for the implementation</i></p>	<p><i>Chapter 5. Pilot Results & Assessment Plan: the Baseline values</i></p> <p><i>Chapter 6. Focusing on Cold ironing – Opportunities, needs and governance framework</i></p> <p><i>Chapter 7. Cold ironing development strategy</i></p> <p><i>Chapter 8. Cold Ironing Action Plan and recommendations</i></p>	<p><i>perspective of the cold-ironing solution in key Inland Waterways in Italy, a thorough assessment of its feasibility is provided along with a development strategy and implementation plan.</i></p> <p><i>In particular, key outcomes paving the way to further steps such as an action plan and inputs for future activities aiming at the design model of a typical plant are outlined.</i></p>
<p>Task 7.3 Corridor management & organizational models for sustainability, resilience and competitiveness of the territorial synchromodal transport system</p>	<p><i>Overall, this task will implement different applications of WP3 Corridor management:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>· Implementation of Task 3.2 guidelines to produce a GAP analysis.</i> <i>· A new smart daily bulletin of navigability conditions.</i> <i>· Implementation and test of Task 3.4 outputs on Corridor visibility and common open data platform, including the potentialities of cold ironing as a specific network of facilities, aimed at realizing a fully functional corridor equipped/ready for IWW future mobility.</i> 	<p><i>Chapter 2 Italian River Pilot Baseline situation and objectives</i></p> <p><i>Chapter 3. Pilot specification</i></p> <p><i>Chapter 4. Pilot Execution Plan</i></p> <p><i>Chapter 5. Pilot Results & Assessment Plan: the Baseline values</i></p> <p><i>Chapter 8. Cold Ironing Action Plan and recommendations</i></p>	<p><i>A general overview and update is provided with reference to all the applications being addressed, also leading to the synchromodal corridor management system (SCMS). Moreover, a specific deal is paid to cold ironing feasibility key outcomes paving the way to further steps such as an action and implementation plan are outlined also taking into account the governance model to be applied and possible replicability in the wider context.</i></p>

Task Governance: Living labs activation and management	7.4 <i>Setting up a sustainable stakeholders partnership for longer term collaboration through the living lab concept in order to develop a resilient, more competitive and more entrepreneurial regional inland waterways transport and logistic economy.</i>	<i>Chapter 2 Italian River Pilot Baseline situation and objectives</i> <i>Chapter 3. Pilot specification</i> <i>Chapter 4. Pilot Execution Plan</i> <i>Chapter 5. Pilot Results & Assessment Plan: the Baseline values</i>	<i>A general overview and update is provided with particular reference to the baseline conditions as well as the implementation plan.</i>
Task 7.5 Digital twin		<i>Chapter 2 Italian River Pilot Baseline situation and objectives</i> <i>Chapter 3. Pilot specification</i> <i>Chapter 4. Pilot Execution Plan</i> <i>Chapter 5. Pilot Results & Assessment Plan: the Baseline values</i>	<i>A general overview and update is provided with particular reference to the baseline conditions as well as the implementation plan.</i>

1.3. Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The scope of this deliverable is not only to describe the objectives, the tools/systems to be addressed, the execution plan and the KPIs applied for the Italian IWW pilot but also to present the key results of the study of a possible implementation of the cold-ironing solution along the canals Fissero-Tartaro-Canalbianco-Po di Levante and Po-Brondolo.

Therefore, in the deliverable, five main sections can be identified that are:

- **Section 1** (chapter 2) where is described the actual scenarios of the Padano-Veneto IWW with a focus of the two segments considered in the pilot: the Po River from Cremona to the mouth in the Adriatic Sea and the canals Fissero-Tartaro-Canalbianco-Po di Levante and Po-Brondolo. Besides information about the traffic flows, and the IWW governance, the stakeholders are provided together with a SWOT analysis of the IWW.
- **Section 2** (chapter 3) where the specification of the pilot is provided, emphasising its objectives and tools/systems; the description includes those developed directly within the pilot, such as the

navigability conditions prediction model, the smart bulletin, the cold-ironing feasibility study and the gap analysis, as well as the ones developed in other WPs of the Project and customized on the basis of the Italian IWW scenario such as the Digital Twin, the Synchro-modality Corridor Management System, the Acoustic emission SHM system and the Fiber Optic Sensor system. Moreover, the Living Lab approach, followed to interact with the stakeholder in order to listen their needs and gather their feeling about the tools/systems considered in the pilot is described.

- **Section 3** (chapter 4) where for each tool/system addressed in the Italian pilot, the related execution plan with the results reached up to July 2024 is illustrated.
- **Section 4** (chapter 5) illustrates the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) selected in order to evaluate the results of the Italian pilot, the innovation plan and the contribution of the tools/systems considered to the expected impact of CRISTAL project at the regional and EU level.
- **Section 5** (from chapter 6 to chapter 8) where the feasibility study about cold-ironing implementations along the Italian canals is described.

The remaining parts of the document are the executive summary (chapter 1) and the conclusions (chapter 9), as well as the references, the list of tables, the list of figures, and the appendices (annexes).

2. Italian River Pilot scenario

This section is dedicated to developing and explaining the general context of the Italian pilot. This explanation allows to detail the aim of the pilot, that can be found in the next section.

2.1. Pilot Case IWW infrastructure scenario

The Italian pilot covers some inland waters that are part of the “Padano-Veneto” inland waterway systems described in the following paragraph.

2.1.1. “Padano-Veneto” inland waterway system

The “Padano-Veneto” inland waterway system corresponds to the Northern Italy inland waterway system whose strategic and priority importance has been recognised at national level with the law 380/1990. In particular, (moving progressively from west to east along the Po Valley), it consists of:

- the Po River (from Piacenza to the main river mouth)
- the Mantua-Adriatic Sea Canal (Fissero - Tartaro - Canalbianco - Po di Levante),
- the Po-Brondolo canal, linking the previous one with the Venice Lagoon, which is also part of the system;
- the “Litoranea veneta” waterway;
- the “Idrovia Ferrarese” waterway;
- the inland ports of Cremona, Mantua, Rovigo, Ferrara and Porto Nogaro (and other public and private docks along the waterway);
- the North Adriatic Sea ports, such as Ravenna, Chioggia, Venice, Monfalcone and Trieste.

Figure 1 The Padano Veneto waterway system

Source: Own elaboration

The Po River and the Mantua-Adriatic Sea Canal (Fissero-Tartaro-Canalbianco-Po di Levante) are the two main waterways that synergistically connect the sea to the heart of the Po Valley, in an east-west direction where the inland ports are located.

According to the European classification (CEMT), both waterways belong or are meant to be upgraded to navigability category V, while others are classified with lower values (see the following figure).

However, it is important to point out that each of these two main waterways, closely located and mutually interconnected while running almost parallel in an east-west direction, has a distinct character.

In fact, the Po River waterway corresponds to a major part of the largest natural river in Italy, characterized primarily by a free-flow regime, which implies limited navigability conditions during certain periods due to seasonal variations.

On the other hand, the Mantua-Adriatic Sea Canal is a closely regulated system (as testified by the number of locks along its path), which allows for year-round navigability.

Despite current situation of certain sections, the importance of the waterway system is testified also by the acknowledgment of many sections and nodes as part of the TEN-T network, and in particular of the Baltic-Adriatic and Mediterranean Corridors.

Figure 2 The Padano-Veneto waterways system within the core and comprehensive TEN-T network

Source: TENtec portal

Figure 3 The Padano Veneto waterway system within the CNC of the TEN-T network
Source: TENtec portal

Within this overall system, the Italian pilot in CRISTAL, in particular focuses on the following IWW sections:

- Po river from Cremona to the river mouth (river);
- Fissero - Tartaro - Canalbianco - Po di Levante (canal);
- Po – Brondolo (canal).

The infrastructure operator of the first section is AIPo while Infrastrutture Venete is the infrastructure operator of the other two. Both AIPo and Infrastrutture Venete (IV) are partner of CRISTAL Project.

Figure 4 The Padano Veneto waterway system – zoomed view on the main IWW
Source: Own elaboration

In the proceeding of the deliverable, the term Fissero – Tartaro – Canalbianco waterway will be used to jointly indicate the two Fissero – Tartaro – Canalbianco – Po di Levante and Po – Brondolo canals, unless otherwise specified.

2.1.2. Cremona-Mantua-Po River mouth (infrastructure operator: AIPo)

The Po River waterway corresponds to a major part of the largest natural river in Italy, characterized primarily by a free-flow regime, which implies limited navigability conditions during certain periods due to seasonal variations.

The water level can change according to the meteorological events (raining, snow melting, draught, etc..) and the request of water for the irrigations of the cultivated fields or for industrial processes (the Po River basin crosses the economic heart of Italy). Moreover, the river current and events such as floods can move the sand and the debris on the riverbed accumulating them in some critical points (shallow water points) reducing the depth of the river. Therefore, the navigability conditions, in terms of the possibility for a class V vessel to have enough water to navigate, change over time.

The Po River is navigable from Cremona to the sea over approximately 280 km. Its direct outlet to the sea is not functional, but it connects through the Po di Levante to Porto Levante and the Po - Brondolo waterway to the ports of Chioggia and Venice.

Figure 5 River Po infrastructure managed by AIPo (in orange colour)

Source: Own elaboration

2.1.3. Fissero – Tartaro – Canalbianco – Po di Levante and Po-Brondolo canals (infrastructure operator: Infrastrutture Venete)

Infrastrutture Venete will focus its study along two main branches of the IWW, represented by Fissero-Tartaro-Canalbianco-Po di Levante and Po-Brondolo canals (see the following figures) providing, respectively, the outlets to the Adriatic Sea and the Venice lagoon. Hereafter, for the sake of simplicity, the entire system will be referred to as the “Fissero-Tartaro-Canalbianco waterway” (implicitly also including the Po di Levante and Po-Brondolo sections).

Figure 6 Fissero-Tartaro-Canalbianco-Po di Levante canal
Source: Own elaboration

Figure 7 Po-Brondolo canal
Source: Own elaboration

It is to underline that, being a regional level operator owned by Veneto region, IV is not directly managing the initial part of the waterway, located in Lombardy region (namely in the Mantua province). Nonetheless, according to a systemic and comprehensive approach, the study will be extended to the whole length of the IWW.

With reference to the whole IV network, the overall administration of such infrastructures also includes the need to take into consideration the management of more than 30 navigation locks (i.e. *conche di navigazione*), several piers and slides (i.e. *pontili e scivoli*) as well as both fix and mobile bridges that are allowing the full exploitation of the waterway.

The waterway is exploiting the connectivity of important areas of the territory of Veneto and Lombardy, thus allowing to directly interconnect the Adriatic Sea with inland areas that are easily reachable through inland navigation. In this regard, exemplifying also other minor waterways connected to the main ones through a concrete example, the case of Idrovia Litoranea Veneta, is relevant as well.

Within Veneto Region, such branches of the IWW are then directly managed by Infrastrutture Venete Srl in collaboration with the local Inspectorates (i.e. *ispettorati di porto*), which contribute to a proper and smooth use of such infrastructure.

2.2. “Padano-Veneto” inland waterway infrastructure: governance

The governance of the Padano-Veneto inland waterway, which constitutes a strategic asset for the Italian nation (law 380/1990), is rather complex and involves several actors with different responsibilities.

The Italian Ministry of Transport and Infrastructure is responsible for safety and security of inland waterways, while the Regions are responsible for managing inland waterways infrastructures in their respective territories (D. Lgs 112/1998). The regions delegate the most operational functions relating to the management of the waterway system to third-party bodies, keeping only the programming proposals in their hands.

For flood protection and water resources management, the activities are coordinated by District Authorities, established after the Water Framework Directive (Directive water 2000/60/CE), that respond directly to the Italian Ministry for the Environment and Energetic Safety. The Padano-Veneto inland waterway system falls within the territory of the Po River District Authority and the Eastern Alps District Authority.

Navigation infrastructures along the Po River must be planned and realized in coherence and accordance with flood risk mitigation objectives, set out in the Po district Flood Risk Management Plan, and with environmental objectives, defined in the Po River Basin Management Plan, as required by the Flood Directive 2006/60/CE, and the Water Directive 2000/60/CE.

Design of navigation infrastructures along the Po River must be approved by the Po River district Authority, that has to verify their environmental and safety compatibility.

The Regions involved with the Padano-Veneto waterway system are Piedmont, Lombardy, Emilia-Romagna, Veneto and Friuli-Venezia Giulia. The first four Regions signed an agreement, the “Interregional agreement for navigation on the river Po”; the management method of the system itself is coordinated, and the costs are shared.

As the Italian pilot focuses on some sections of the Padano-Veneto inland waterway system (i.e. the Po River from Cremona to the mouth and the two canals Fissero–Tartaro–Canalbianco-Po di Levante e Po-Brondolo) the reference Regions are Lombardy, Emilia-Romagna and Veneto.

Each of these three Regions signed an “Agreement” with an inland waterway infrastructure operator for pooling in the exercise of inland navigation functions.

In particular, Lombardy and Emilia-Romagna have delegated to the Interregional Agency for the Po River (Agenzia Interregionale per il fiume Po - AIPo), the management of the navigability along the fairway with daily survey and dredging in addition to the design and construction of the works aimed at improving navigability conditions such as groynes.

Furthermore, AIPo manages the functioning of different navigation locks along the Po River and the Lombardy reaches of the Fissero-Tartaro-Canalbianco system.

Veneto Region identified Infrastrutture Venete (IV) as the operator of the regional inland navigation network (that includes the Fissero - Tartaro - Canalbianco - Po di Levante canal and Po – Brondolo canal) and, since January 1st 2020, of the regional railway infrastructures. Therefore, IV manages the system of locks and hydraulic supports that compose the Veneto internal navigation network, is responsible for dredging the inland waterways, and has also a mediation/coordination role with several other institutions of the territory that have to be coordinated, e.g. for the management of mobile bridges.

As already said, both Agenzia Interregionale per il fiume Po and Infrastrutture Venete are partners of CRISTAL project.

2.3. Traffic flows

The waterway system addressed by the Italian pilot is characterised by limited traffic volumes if compared with other EU countries. Nonetheless, it is to register relevant flows with reference to specific commodities and in passenger transport, the latter being strongly related to the touristic potentials of the area.

More specifically, as far as freight transport is concerned, the following table provides an overview of transported commodities according to the NST 2007 classification¹.

1 The NST 2007 classification system, standing for "Nomenclature uniforme des marchandises pour les Statistiques de Transport" is a European standard designed to categorize goods for transport statistics.

Table 2 Annual Transported goods in the Padano-Veneto waterway system – year 2021.

Source: CNIT

NST CODE	DESCRIPTION	TONNES	TONNES – KM
1	Products of agriculture, hunting, and forestry; fish and other fishing products	66,773	9,638,354
2	Coal and lignite; crude petroleum and natural gas	72,468	8,068,740
3	Metal ores and other mining and quarrying products; peat; uranium and thorium	13,064	29,827
6	Wood and products of wood and cork (except furniture); articles of straw and plaiting materials; pulp, paper and paper products; printed matter and recorded media	157	4,117
7	Coke and refined petroleum products	107,352	15,566,040
8	Chemicals, chemical products, and man-made fibers; rubber and plastic products; nuclear fuel	178,045	26,428,725
10	Basic metals; fabricated metal products, except machinery and equipment	184,127	27,390,201
11	Machinery and equipment n.e.c.; office machinery and computers; electrical machinery and apparatus n.e.c.; radio, television and communication equipment and apparatus; medical, precision and optical instruments; watches and clocks	7,340	1,917,407
12	Transport equipment	10	60
14	Secondary raw materials; municipal wastes and other wastes	4,000	662,400
16	Equipment and material utilized in the transport of goods	347,092	50,328,340
TOTAL		980,428	140,034,204

It is worth noting the significant share (35%) accounted for by NST group 16, which includes various types of transport equipment—not necessarily limited to unitized cargo within containers, but also covering items like containers or trailers as manufactured goods. Relevant percentages, beyond 10%, are associated with NTS groups 10 (Basic metals; fabricated metal products, except machinery and equipment), 8 (Chemicals, chemical products, and man-made fibers, rubber and plastic products) and 7 (Coke and refined petroleum products).

Figure 8 Distribution according to the NST 2007 categories of the freight traffic volumes on the Padano-Veneto IWW system in 2021

Source: Italian Ministry of Infrastructures and Transport, 2023

As regards passenger transport, it is to mention different typologies of traffic and vessels, also including relevant flows associated to tourism. These last categories imply different kinds of units ranging from leisure boats to river cruise ships. Obviously, the former represent the highest figures in terms of the number of vessels while the latter can accommodate a higher number of visitors and carrying out longer trips, thus contributing to the number of incoming tourists. Furthermore, they are mainly associated with sustainable tourism approach also pivoting on intermodal connections and active modes (especially linking to cycleways and local paths).

Considering all the different typologies of registered vessels the majority are leisure boats, while 8% are commercial units (almost half of the passages being referred to empty ones).

Overall, the historical series of the last years show remarkable increases especially in freight transport and a limited decline in passengers transport which could also be related to the COVID-19 pandemic (see the following figure on both freight and passenger transport).

Figure 9 Historical series of transported tonnes and passengers in the 2013-2021 period

Source: Italian Ministry of Infrastructures and Transport, 2023

2.4. Stakeholders

In addition to the public administrations (especially the regional ones) and the infrastructure managers in charge of constructing, maintaining and managing the infrastructures, various other stakeholders are somehow impacted and interested by the Italian IWW system.

In this regard, the list of the Italian IWW stakeholders and the map of their commercial relationship are respectively in Table 3 and Figure 10².

² This information can also be found in deliverable 4.1 “Detailed requirements for the governance framework”: chapter 3.3 and chapter 4.3 respectively.

Table 3 Pilot's stakeholders' classification

Source: Italian pilot

	Main actors	Detailed actors	Italian Case
Transport function	Infrastructure manager		
		Rail	RFI, Infrastrutture Venete
		Road	Core Network highways close to the IWW: Autostrada del Brennero Spa (A22 Brennero-Modena), Autostrade per l'Italia Spa (A1 Milano-Bologna, A13 Bologna-Padova) Comprehensive Network highways close to the IWW: Autovia padana Spa (A21 Brescia-Piacenza) Anas; Provinces/municipalities for local roads; Veneto Strade spa.
		IWT	AIPo (realising and maintaining the infrastructures to ensure the free-flow navigation along the Po River from Piacenza to Adriatic Sea) Infrastrutture Venete (realising and maintaining the infrastructures for the navigation along the Fissero-Tartaro-Canalbianco-Po di Levante, Po - Brondolo and Litoranea Veneta waterway)
	Transport companies		
		Shipping line	Not regular tourist line services: Altobordo Srl (Motonave Stradivari), River Cruises SRL (Cremona Crociere)
		Trucks	Some of the logistics services providers own their trucks; local trucks owners. (See Logistics service providers)
		Rail freight operators	Mercitalia (RFI Group), HUPAC, Sograf (Porto di Cremona), FS logistica (Porto di Mantova)
		Barge operators	Fagioli Spa, Tecno Service Chioggia, Fluviomar Srl, Omnariver, Transmar Venezia, Caronte Shipping, Ship Service Venezia s.r.l.

	Rail-road terminal		Interporto Quadrante Europa (Verona), Interporto di Bologna spa, Interporto Padova Spa; several terminals in Milano Area.
		Terminal operators	
	IWW Ports		Port of Cremona, Port of Mantova Valdaro, Port of Rovigo
		Terminal operators	Portuali Valdaro S.r.l. (Mantova Valdaro Port - also barge operator)
		Port authority	Province of Cremona (Cremona Port), Provincia di Mantova (Mantova Valdaro Port), Ispettorato di Porto (Rovigo Port)
	Deepsea ports		Marghera Port (Venice) and Ravenna port
		Terminal operators	Several operators in Marghera Port (Venice) and Ravenna Port
		Port authority	ADSP Mare Adriatico Settentrionale (Venezia Port) ADSP Mare Adriatico Centro Settentrionale (Ravenna Port) ASDP Mare Adriatico Orientale (Trieste Port)
	Logistics service providers		
		1 PL (producer delivers cargo to client, own trucks/vessels)	Paganella Spa, Generation Transport spa, Katoen Natie, Fercam, ASTL Logistica Srl, TCF Rosignoli Logistics, Borsari & C Srl, Fagioli Spa (oversize loads), River Service Srl, Maersk, Servizi, Portuali Valdaro S.r.l. (Mantova Port)
		2 PL (producer delivers cargo via transport company)	
		3PL (outsourcing of logistics to a third party)	
		4PL (outsource all of the organisation and oversight of their supply chain and logistics to one external provider which has no own assets)	
			Note 1: Some of these operators provide also a barge service). Note 2: it is not simple to allocate the above operators in 1-2-3-4-5 PL classes

	Shipper / cargo owner		
		Sender/receiver	Consorzio Agrario, Arvedi Spa, Belleli Energy, Marcegaglia, Gruppo Saviola, MOL
Regulation	Regulators of IWT		
		EU	Yes Please note that Po River is still not considered a transnational IWW system
		Country government	Ministero delle Infrastrutture e dei Trasporti: Inland navigation management
		Local government (Regional)	Lombardy Region, Emilia-Romagna Region, Veneto Region, Piedmont Region: responsible for the development of the inland waterway in their respective territory (Interregional agreement on inland navigation to coordinate the actions)
		Basin Authorities	Autorità di Bacino Distrettuale del Fiume Po: flood protection and water resources management (refers to the Ministero dell'Ambiente e della Sicurezza Energetica)
Public interest	People		
		Citizens living near the waterway	Yes
		Environmental group(s)	WWF, Legambiente, Associazione Persona Ambiente
		Local interest groups	Propeller Club Mantova, UNII
		Civil Protections Organisation	National and Regional Civil Protection Departments and Civil Protection Offices within Municipalities
Linked industries to IWT	Sector organisations representing private companies		
		Chambers of Commerce	Unioncamere (nation level), regional/local Chambers of Commerce, Uniontrasporti (competence center of the Chambers of Commerce)
		Farmers	Associations: Confagricoltura, Coldiretti, CIA, Libera associazione agricoltori cremonesi

		Power plants	ENEL
		Tourism sector	<i>Not regular tourist line services:</i> Altobordo Srl (Motonave Stradivari), River Cruises SRL (Cremona Crociere), Motonavi Andes Negrini (Mantova) Several other companies operating on Laguna Veneta and other section of the Padano-Veneto IWW system (not in the area selected for the pilot)
		Shipyards	C.N.P, Cantiere Navale Visentini, Cantiere Navale Vittoria, CGX Costruzioni Generali XODO Srl
		Others	Rowing Clubs, several other associations for sporting purpose.
Researchers	Universities		
		University 1	Several universities in Lombardy, Veneto and Emilia-Romagna occasionally work on specific projects related to the IWW such as Università Ca' Foscari, Università degli studi di Padova, Università di Parma, Università di Mantova, Politecnico di Milano.
		University n	
	Knowledge institutes		
		Knowledge institute 1	Corila (consortium)

This representation allows to visualise the complex set of relationship which are to be involved when addressing the governance of the IWW for purposes of living labs or pilot activities to be carried out. However, the picture could be even more complex when considering the actual numbers of actors corresponding to each category, also considering a quite fragmented economic system as well as the presence of different administration and agencies due to a non-centralised institutional framework.

Figure 10 Actors with a direct contractual relationship in the Italian pilot case
Source: Cristal project D.4.1

2.5. SWOT analysis

In this paragraph a SWOT analysis specifically related to the Italian waterway system addressed by the WP7 pilot is reported. Hence, in comparison with the SWOT realised in the framework of WP1 considering the project objective “a resilient inland waterway infrastructure for transport”, the present one has a more specific and focused scope.

Strength

- In general, inland waterways transport has relevant competitiveness factors in terms of sustainability opportunities and reliability:
 - By CO₂ emission: it produces 5 times less by tonne transported than road transport;
 - By its reliability: no congestion reported inland waterway network can be compared to a disturbance of any other transport mode;
 - By its security: very few thefts or accidents are reported on IWT.
- The infrastructure managers are providing the access to the network and related services (e.g. locks) to users free of charge.
- In the case of the Fissero–Tartaro–Canalbianco waterway full operativity 24/7 is ensured throughout the year (thus linking Mantova port and Rovigo port with Adriatic Sea ones).

- For specific transport (e.g. exceptional transports carrying oversized loads) the waterway solution is a valid alternative for overcoming specific limitation and criticalities of the other transport networks.

Weaknesses

- The coverage and length of the main rivers and canal network is more limited than in other EU countries, also due to the geomorphological reasons.
- Though the Po River basin encompasses the main industrial area of Italy the river itself (especially in its navigable sections) does not cross the main cities.
- Some physical bottlenecks are hampering the possibility of relevant connections along the network.
- Inland waterways logistics has a limited market share with respect to other modes of transport.
- The fragmented governance poses challenges in addressing the relevant shared challenges of the system.
- From the users' perspective, setting up and organising an intermodal waterway transport is more complex (especially in comparison with the road alternative) and requests certain dimensional thresholds to be met in order to be economically viable and justified.

Opportunities

- Several projects are ongoing to enhance IWW, addressing in particular the removal of relevant (though local) physical bottlenecks, thus unlocking relevant opportunities on a broader level.
- The acknowledgment as relevant sections of the TEN-T core networks are supporting, also though co-funding opportunities, the strategic development of the mentioned IWWs.
- Growing sensibility from the general public as well as stakeholders are pushing for the development of more sustainable transport solutions as the IWW.

Threats

- With particular to the free flow waterway sections, global warming, extreme conditions leading to either drought or flooding episodes are more and more frequent and violent, which increase risks on hydraulic structures.

3. Pilot specification

The Italian pilot aims to improve the asset management and promote the navigability of the Italian inland waterways' infrastructure, with a focus on Po River and Fissero–Tartaro–Canalbianco waterway using new technologies and considering green and environmental impacts and improvement of the resilience.

More in details, three are the main objectives of the pilot: to increase the reliability of the IWW, to improve the sustainability and finally to make the preventive maintenance of locks and the riverbed more effective.

Based on the objective considered, specific tools/systems were selected for the pilot.

In the following paragraph 3.1, for each pilot objectives the tools/systems selected are described.

Furthermore, in paragraph 3.2, the Living Lab approach, used to establish a collaborative relationship with IWW stakeholders to listen to their needs, to collect their opinions on the tools/systems considered in the pilot project and to identify the elements that, if solved, could favour the development of the Italian IWW, is illustrated.

3.1. Tools/systems addressed in the Italian River Pilot

In the following paragraphs the tools/systems that will be addressed in the Italian River Pilot are presented with also the motivation of the choice.

3.1.1. Tools/systems to improve the reliability of the IWW

The reliability of IWW is the result of the reliability of several elements, from the infrastructure components to the “services”, with the related quality, that are provided to the users.

Since the Po is a free-flowing river, i.e. without water level control as in canals, providing information on current and forecast navigability conditions to users of the waterway (logistics operators, barge operators, tourist boat operators...) is essential. Today AIPo produces a daily notice to skippers bulletin covering the Po River stretch from Cremona to its mouth in the Adriatic Sea with information about navigability conditions with a three-days horizon.

For better planning of their business activities, inland waterway transport and logistics operators would need information on the navigability conditions of the Po River covering a longer time horizon, making them more confident in using this inland waterway.

Furthermore, for transport and logistics operators and more generally for users of the “Padano-Veneto” inland waterway system it could be very useful to have information on the warnings that, at different levels, could impact the usability of the inland waterway and, in the event of an interruption, receive support to decide what to do to meet their commitment on the delivery of the goods.

Therefore, a set of tools/systems has been selected for the Italian pilot: some of them are specifically for the Po River (navigability conditions prediction model and smart bulletin), while others could find

application in any inland waterway, such as the Digital Twin and the Synchro-modal Corridor Management System.

3.1.1.1. Navigability conditions prediction model

As anticipated, the Po River is a free-flow river without any control of the water level as in a canal.

The water level can change according to the meteorological events (rain, snow melting, draught, ...) and the request of water for the irrigation of the cultivated fields or for industrial processes (the Po River crosses the economic heart of Italy).

Moreover, the river current and events such as floods can move the sand and the debris on the riverbed accumulating them in some critical points (shallow water point) reducing the depth of the river.

Therefore, the navigability conditions, in terms of the possibility for a class V vessel to have enough water to navigate, change over time.

Today, AIPo publishes a daily report with information about the navigability conditions in the critical point of the Po River covering a period of three days.

But three days is a short time horizon for planning a freight transport along the waterway considering that a trip from Cremona to the Adriatic Sea along the Po River takes on average 3-4 days for a one-way trip and more or less 10 days for a two-way trip.

Therefore, with the aim of supporting logistics operators in planning river transport, an algorithm for predicting navigability conditions along the Po River from Cremona to the mouth of the river in the Adriatic Sea at 10 days will be developed as part of the Italian pilot.

This algorithm will be based on a statistical model plus a Machine Learning model that make the predictions having in input the same dataset, some measured and some forecasted, at specific points (critical points) along the river.

The dataset will be composed by data of:

- Water levels measured by hydrometers;
- Water depth measured daily by dedicated AIPo personnel called "meatore" in Italian;
- Forecasted discharges provided by the hydrological models from "Flood and Drought Early Warning System (FEWS/DEWS) already in use in AIPo.

These two models will elaborate the data in a different way (statistical approach and ML-Long-Short-Term-Memory) and will produce outputs equivalent from the navigability point of view in each critical point: the navigation probability for each class of vessel in the case of the statistical model and the water depth (from which can be easily derived the navigation probability for each class of vessel) in case of the ML model.

The "precision" of the forecasts produced by each model, together with the effort required, will be compared and evaluated with the aim of identifying the "solution" for a forecast, of the navigability conditions, as reliable as possible.

The Po River stretches from Mantua to its month is divided into nine sections (river reaches) as represented in Figure 11): since there may be more than one critical point in each section, (the point where the navigability conditions are forecasted) the section navigability will be calculated considering the worst data among those of all the critical points in the section.

Figure 11 Po River sections (or river reaches)

Source: AIPo

The navigability conditions predictions at section level will be sent to the DT for further elaboration and to AIPo internal IT systems to be included in the “smart bulletin” to the skippers.

The availability of reliable forecasts of the navigability conditions will be of interest of several stakeholders: from the IWW transport and logistic operators to better program their shipments, to the IWW tourist operator to better plan their tourist trips, to the IWW infrastructure operator (AIPo) to arrange a timely and preventive dredging action.

The final effect will be an improvement of the reliability of the IWW as a mode of transport of goods and passengers which could be the basis for attracting investments for further development of the waterway.

3.1.1.2. Smart bulletin

The 10 days forecasts of the navigability conditions, at section level, covering the Po River from Mantua up to its mouth in the Adriatic Sea, developed by the prediction model, must be communicated or at least must be available to the IWW users.

The current “notice to skippers” daily bulletin produced by AIPo is not adequate considering the amount of data to be communicated and the graphical possibilities offered by the IT technologies: therefore, a new and smart bulletin is required.

In the pilot, graphical and effective solutions to represent the navigability conditions along the Po River distinguished between the CEMT class of the vessels will be studied and implemented considering the communications media used.

3.1.1.3. DT (developed in WP5)

One of the objectives of the pilot is to identify solutions that could help to improve the reliability of the Italian IWW. In this regards the use of a Digital Twin (DT), with the associated analysis methods, that elaborate data from different sources and provides insight about the actual and future status of the IWW infrastructure or the usability of the IWW could be useful for an infrastructure operator and indirectly for the users (logistic and transport operator, tourist operator up to the yachtsman).

Considering the specificity of the Padano-Veneto IWW system (i.e. the Italian IWW) and the objectives of the pilot, some DT use-case of potential interest for the Italian infrastructure operators were discussed and agreed with WP5.

The DT use-cases with the higher potential interest for the Italian case are the following:

- Prediction of water depth (through ML) using hydrological information (I-2);
- Display of measured water level from hydrometer network: DT Smart Monitor (I-3);
- Alert functionality for navigability due to hydrological issues (I-4);
- Acoustic Emission (AE) System – Display of outputs (I-6).

The first three are related to the assess and predict the navigability along the Po River while the last one is connected to check and visualise the structural health of a lock door.

The input data for the use-cases I-2, I-3 and I-4 will come from the sensors and measurements performed by AIPo while the input data for the use-case I-6 will be gathered by CERTH as part of the activity of WP5 during one or two measurement campaigns at the Baricetta lock doors and Isola Serafini lock doors.

3.1.1.4. SCMS (developed in WP3)

A Synchro-modal Corridor Management System for inland waterways will be developed within the project to address the challenges emerging from natural and human caused disruptions.

The SCMS is intended to be a system that will aggregate information related to the prediction of natural or human caused disruptions in the inland waterways, assessing their operational impacts and timely disseminating this knowledge to stakeholders of the inland waterways transport systems, providing also suggestion for alternative routes for the delivery of the goods, with the aim to support their decision-making process

The SCMS, developed in WP3, has various components providing specific services, among which those of interest to the Italian pilot have been identified, considering the peculiarities of the Padano-Veneto waterway system:

- Early detection and info service;
- Impact identification service;
- Decision support to action.

For the description of these services, please refer to the deliverable D3.1

These services must be customized based on the Italian pilot scenario. Therefore, data and information (such as for example, IWW digital map, the origin/destination matrix of goods moved by each of the three main inland ports, Cremona, Mantua and Rovigo, ...) on the Po River corridor were collected and transferred to WP3 for the implementation.

The 10-day forecasts of navigability conditions, produced by the forecast model, will also be sent to the SCMS because they are the inputs for some of its elaborations.

3.1.2. Tools/systems to improve the sustainability of the IWW

The sustainability of what we do and how we do it is becoming increasingly important to ensure the future of our planet.

While environmental impact and a green approach (including reducing our CO₂ footprint) must be taken into account in what we do and how we do it, we must also be prepared for the effects of climate change by protecting and preserving our activities and our business.

As in the case of reliability, many elements contribute to the sustainability of an inland waterway. The Italian pilot has decided to focus on two of these: the supply of electricity, hopefully produced from green and renewable sources to vessels and the procedures for the business continuity of operators and public bodies to the impacts of climate change on the waterway.

As regards the first aspect, the pilot will develop a feasibility study for the implementation of a cold-ironing system on the quays along the Fissero–Tartaro–Canalbianco waterway while, for the second, an assessment (GAP analysis) will be carried out of the compliance of the organizational models of private companies and public bodies operating along the “Padano-Veneto” waterway system with international standards and EU policies on resilience and business continuity to climate change.

3.1.2.1. Cold ironing

Infrastrutture Venete will contribute to CRISTAL activities by delivering a feasibility study testing the possibility of developing a dedicated network of cold ironing facilities along the two branches of the managed IWW managed (see chapter 2.1.3) and exploring the possibility of further replicability along others, mainly touristic routes, such as the Idrovia Litoranea Veneta. The detailed definition of the technologies to be developed and installed for this purpose is part of the expected outcomes of the study to be carried out.

The feasibility study will face the challenge of providing shoreside electrical power for the energy demands of ships calling at port/berths, allowing them to switch off their auxiliary diesel generators (and consequently reducing related gas and noise emissions). Furthermore, the new infrastructure will be ready to receive innovative boats as well as to fully follow the EU Commission’s indications on a decarbonized transport future.

IV is focusing on the topic of energy supply to boats using the waterway and in particular on the possibility to develop a dedicated supporting infrastructure to provide both renewable energy production at local

level and an adequate typology of devices to be used for charging e-boats or for plug-in services for boats. Details of such technologies are provided in the second part of the present deliverable (see chapter 6 and the following ones).

3.1.2.2. GAP analysis

With the objective to raise awareness among the IWW Italian stakeholders of the need to organize themselves to increase their resilience to the impact of climate changes, a GAP analysis has been proposed to a sample of these stakeholders. This analysis aims to assess if the organizational model of an entity (private company or public body) complies with the climate change mitigation and adaptation international standards and EU policies (identified in task 3.2) and is able to ensure resilience to the impacts of climate change and smooth functioning of its businesses/activities/operations related to the IWW in case of extreme events. The GAP analysis focused on four main topics: managements systems, ESG reporting status, mitigation and adaptation actions to contrast climate change and how to guarantee business continuity.

The objective is to perform the GAP analysis for fifteen stakeholders of which ten private companies and five public bodies. The stakeholders will not be pre-selected, but the GAP analysis will be performed upon request of the stakeholder. Therefore, several communication and dissemination actions will be put in place to inform IWW stakeholders of this opportunity.

3.1.3. Tools/systems for a preventive maintenance

The third objective of the pilot is related to the maintenance and more specifically to the preventive maintenance of two critical elements of an inland waterway such as the “Padano-Veneto” waterway system: the locks and the riverbed where the accumulation of sand and debris, typical of a free-flowing river, reducing the depth of the water, compromises the navigation of vessels of a given class.

As for the locks, it was decided to investigate the potential of applying acoustic emission technology to assess the structural health of the metal part of the lock doors.

For the estimation of the height of the accumulations of sand and debris in a point of a river, a Fiber Optic Sensor system will be developed at prototype level in the laboratory where a context like that of the Po River will be recreated. Knowing in real time the height of the water at critical points for the navigation of the river (instead of measuring this height manually every day) would allow for better planning of the dredging of the river.

3.1.3.1. Acoustic emissions SHM

Considering the “Padano-Veneto” IWW, there are locks not only along the Fissero-Tartaro-Canalbianco-Po di Levante and Po-Brondolo (about 12) but also along the Po River from Cremona to the Adriatic Sea (about 4) and in other minor waterways: the locks are key infrastructures of the IWW, as not only failures but also maintenance interventions have a significant impact on the usability of the waterway.

The availability of a tool that allows to make predictions of possible faults of a lock's door could be very useful for an infrastructure operator.

Thanks to AE technology, it is possible to collect data on the state of the metal infrastructure of a lock, which will then be processed to predict possible future failures. For the description of this technology and its application to produce data that can be used to trigger preventive maintenance actions please refer to the deliverable 2.1 "Interface specification and system architecture preliminary requirements".

To explore the potential of the application of the AE technology, a campaign of AE measurement involving two locks (Baricetta and Isola Serafini) was planned together with WP5 (reference CERTH). In this activity the involvement of the Italian pilot (AIPo and IV) is limited to grant the access to the locks for the measurement and received the report of the results (after the elaboration of data in WP 5 - Digital Twin).

3.1.3.2. Fiber Optic Sensor System

The Fiber Optic Sensor System (FOS) is designed for the real-time and continuous monitoring of navigability conditions in free-flowing waterways such as the Po River. The system will measure the strain levels due to the additional sediment on the bottom of a river.

The description of the FOS can be found in deliverable 2.1 "Interface specification and system architecture preliminary requirements".

3.2. Po River Living Lab

Living Labs (LLs) are open innovation ecosystems in real-life environments using iterative feedback processes throughout a lifecycle approach of an innovation to create sustainable impact. They focus on co-creation, rapid prototyping & testing and scaling-up innovations & businesses, providing (different types of) joint value to the involved stakeholders.

In this context, living labs operate as intermediaries/orchestrators among citizens, research organizations, companies and government agencies/levels.

Taking a broader perspective than the one based on contractual relationships (in chapter 2.4 Stakeholders) and assuming a quadruple-helix model (Yawson, 2009), the relationships among different stakeholders' groups have been depicted in Figure 12.

Users, the core-element of a LL according to EnOLL definition, include ship and barge operators, shipping and logistic companies and manufacturers.

Figure 12 Different relationships between stakeholders' categories
Source: Own elaboration

The correlations among them outlined each group's needs and expectations (Figure 13). This information was considered in planning LL events, to avoid arguments and ensure that each group received a reward for promoting its participation in the LL.

Figure 13 Different relationships between stakeholders' categories.
Source: Own elaboration

Through the living labs, the Italian pilot aims to establish a sustainable stakeholders' partnership between the Project and the various river stakeholders (authorities, policymakers, companies, end-users, etc.) to develop a common view on the "Padano-Veneto" waterway governance and facilitate the acceptance of the CRISTAL technologies and systems.

Therefore in the Italian pilot two types of Living Labs will be put in place: the *living lab – cycle governance* with the aim to reach a common view (Manifesto) on the elements that, if solved, could favour the development of the Italian IWW and the *living lab – cycle technologies* to collect stakeholders' comments and opinions on the tools/systems considered in the Italian pilot and more in general in CRISTAL Project.

4. Pilot execution plan

In this section, for each tool/system illustrated in chapter 3, the steps for their development will be described starting from those developed within WP7, and then moving on to those developed in other WPs and customized for the Italian scenario.

For the tools/systems developed entirely in WP7, the execution plan will also be illustrated, while for the others the information on the execution plan is reported in the deliverables of the reference WP.

4.1. Tools/systems developed in WP7 (Italian pilot)

The tools/systems developed entirely in the Italian pilot are:

- Prediction model;
- Smart bulletin;
- Cold ironing;
- GAP analysis.

4.1.1. Prediction model

Instead of a hydraulic model, it was decided to develop a statistical-based navigability model alongside a machine learning-based navigability model that use the same data collected by AIPo along the Po River from Cremona to its mouth in the Adriatic Sea, and then composite the results to produce a 10-day forecast of navigable conditions.

The input data used to develop and calibrate the two models are:

- *Critical sections of the Po River*, i.e., sections where the accumulation of natural material in riverbed can affect navigability. Statistical data collected: locations and section morphology.
- *Water depth time series i.e.* water depth from monitoring activities mainly during low regimes. The dataset spans from January 1, 1988, to May 12, 2022, and are consisted of 12,294 to 12,255 records, recorded daily, by each measuring stations.
- Riverbed and river discharge time series.
- Outflow scale.
- Basin flow.

The first step was a data preparation activity to pre-process the data (e.g. checks on the stationarity of the time series, seasonal decomposition of the time series). Moreover, the time series data were carefully analysed by handling missing values using the forward fill method to ensure data consistency.

Then, considering the statistical model, a data processing was performed with the elaboration of a first probabilistic method to assess the navigability of the Po River: the time series of historical daily surveys of water depth, collected for more than 30 years, coupled with discharge data available at each monitoring station have been used to define a good estimation of probability of navigability in the critical point of the Po River. These probabilities, joined with the predicted discharge data provided by the *Flood and Drought Early Warning System of the Po River*, EWA system, based on hydrological and hydraulic

models provide a basic method to compute the probability of navigability for each critical point for the next 10 days.

The probability is computed based on the percentage of 15 occurrences of the event *water depth > minimum vessel draft* in the historical data.

This approach allows to define a good statistical correlation between discharges and critical points for water depth in terms of overall performance.

However, this statistic does not consider morphological variations at each critical point due to artificial (i.e. dredging) or natural (e.g. floods) actions. To reduce the uncertainty related to those factors, the idea is to elaborate a method that evaluate the probability value associated to a given day on basis of the values of the previous ones.

As far as the Machine Learning model is concerned, a Long-Short-Term-Memory (LSTM) forecast model has been selected and tested so far to generate the navigability model given the ability of LSTM models to retain information over extended periods.

The two time series datasets, i.e. water depth and water discharge, have been used to extract meaningful insights into the hydrological dynamics under investigation. The water depth time series, delineates variations in depth, enabling an assessment of riverbed topography changes at specified sample stations. Concurrently, the water discharge time series, derived from additional river stations, provides insights into flow dynamics influenced by precipitation, snowmelt, and other hydrological factors.

Using descriptive statistics and visualization techniques, patterns and correlations within these datasets, has been uncovered contributing to a forecast of river navigability.

For each critical point, the results of the two models will be composed in order to have a forecast of the navigability conditions more accurate.

As in each of the nine sections in which the Po River is divided, there could be more than one “critical point” for the navigation (the point where the navigability conditions are calculated), the navigability of a section is calculated considering the worst data among those of all the critical points in the section.

These forecasts will be the input to several systems/tools developed in CRISTAL such as smart bulletin, digital twin and SCMS.

A detailed execution plan is represented in Figure 14.

Figure 14 Navigability conditions prediction model: execution plan
Source: WP 7 elaboration

4.1.2. Smart bulletin

The 10 days forecasts of the navigability conditions, at sections level, covering the Po River from Mantua up to its mouth in the Adriatic Sea have to be communicated or, at least, made available to the IWW users.

The idea is to produce a new version, a “smart” version, of the today “notice to skippers” bulletin to be sent to the IWW users and to make available on the AIPo website.

The graphical presentation of the data will be agreed with WP5 so that the two representations, one in the smart bulletin and the other in the smart DT monitor, are consistent.

AIPo will decide the format of the smart bulletin and the technological solution for its transmission to the IWW users such as skippers, transport and logistic operator. Moreover, it will define the application to access forecast data on its website.

The implementation of the smart bulletin will take place in the second period of the Project and a LL will be used to collect opinions and comments from potential users.

Figure 15 Smart bulletin: execution plan
Source: WP 7 elaboration

4.1.3. Cold ironing feasibility study

IV is currently working on the feasibility study for the realization of a network of cold ironing facilities along the Fissero–Tartaro–Canalbianco waterway.

Furthermore, extension to other IWW, especially Litoranea Veneta has been addressed as well.

In particular, this activity is related to the second part of the present deliverable (D7.1 “RP specification and Baseline measurements”) where the analysis and resulting action plan are presented.

Concerning the implementation process of the related activities, first, relevant preliminary steps have been taken, with reference to the tendering phase of the requested technical expertise. Consequently, technical activities and analyses have started as well.

However, concerning the overall timeline of the activity, it is important to report a limited delay in the related implementation process. More in detail, a more than four-month postponement (from 30/05 to 11/11) in the delivery of D7.1 occurred mainly due to a late start related to changes and new procedural set-up required by the entry in force of the new Italian Public Contract Code (Legislative Decree No. 36/2023). Furthermore, the need to gather feedback from external stakeholders made it difficult to catch up with this delay within the previously set deadline (Month 21).

Nonetheless, the technical activity has mainly been carried out and the key outcomes have already been shared with relevant stakeholders, through an online event (living lab) held on July 9th, 2024.

Figure 16 Cold ironing: execution plan

Source: WP 7 elaboration

Within the analysis, an interdisciplinary approach has been adopted that allows to leverage on synergies related to a vision encompassing:

- Freight and passenger transport with a relevant deal paid to sustainable tourism;
- Intermodality;
- Cold ironing and also recharge of electric units.

Among other things, this implied setting up an action plan with reference to different steps and time horizon. To this end a relevant deal has been paid to the mapping of the state of play and understanding needs and technological solutions.

A key follow-up of the feasibility study (that therefore will be carried out in the second part of the Project) is the development of a design of a "typical plant" model of cold ironing facility (thus paving the way to a possible future implementation beyond the scope and timeline of CRISTAL project). Moreover, this will allow to further consolidate and to finalize preliminary estimations of costs taking into account the relevant weight of auxiliary works and set-up (e.g. wiring and, in case, the realisation of MV/LV

transformer electrical substation), which depend on the very specific conditions of each port/mooring area.

4.1.4. GAP analysis

The first step was to identify the categories of potential beneficiaries of the GAP analysis and group them into public bodies and private companies:

- Public bodies
 - Port (maritime and inland) authorities or equivalent.
 - Municipalities along Po River or Fissero–Tartaro–Canalbianco waterway (preferably with at least a mooring).
- Private companies: manufacturers, logistics or barge operators using/interested in using inland water transport and with a site, preferably, in the pilot area.

After that, the content of Del. 3.2 “Guidelines for the sustainability and resilience of inland water transport and logistics” was reviewed to choose and extract the following relevant topics of discussion and assessment (different combinations of topics applies to different beneficiaries):

- Management systems and ethics obligations (mandatory or voluntary);
- Climate change mitigation and adaptation (awareness level and actions);
- ESG sustainability;
- Business continuity.

Furthermore, it was decided that the output of the GAP analysis would have been delivered to beneficiaries in the form of a short report in Italian.

Finally, questions for each topic and a scoring scheme have been defined: *online questionnaires* have been prepared for each beneficiaries' category and *open questions* to promote discussion have been prepared, as well.

At the same time, an involvement campaign was undertaken, agreed with the other pilot partners, with participation in various events in which, with varying degrees of depth, SOGESCA, after presenting itself and the CRISTAL project, illustrated to the public the opportunities to be subject of the GAP analysis and to participate to the Living Labs.

The first GAP analysis was carried out in December 2023: to date (July 2024), eight GAP analysis have been carried out via interviews or questionnaires (five private companies and three public bodies) and two GAP analysis reports, in Italian, have been produced and delivered to the relevant stakeholders.

A detailed execution plan is represented in Figure 17.

Figure 17 GAP analysis: execution plan

Source: WP 7 elaboration

4.2. Tools/systems developed in other WPs based on the Italian pilot situation

The tools/systems developed in other WPs and then customised on the Italian pilot scenario are:

- Digital Twins: some use-cases;
- Synchro-modal Corridor Management Systems: some features;
- Acoustic emissions SHM: investigation of its use to predict breakages of the metal part of a lock door;
- Fiber Optic Sensor system: in lab prototype.

4.2.1. DT (developed in WP5)

The use cases are prioritized as “Must”, according to the MoSCoW scale, and listed in the part. 3.1.1.3 have been developed based on the data set of critical points along the Po River collected by AIPo in the last 30 years.

More in details:

Prediction of water depth (through ML) using hydrological information (I-2)

To develop UC-I-2 for each critical points along the Po River the related data set coming from daily observations of water depth in those points has been used.

The focus is on obtaining a digital twin supporting the navigation along the river able to forecast:

- a) The specific navigability level in each critical points within each stretch section;
- b) The overall navigability level in each stretch section.

The Po River digital twin has also to relate navigability and alert information to different kinds of vessels and different specific uses (e.g., transport; recreational uses; etc.) and transport loads.

Machine Learning plays an important role in predicting water depth working on available data. For this reason, a ML algorithm to forecast navigability information has been designed. In particular, it will be used a pivotal series of data i.e. daily water depth, gathered from strategically positioned sensor stations in order to extract meaningful insights into the hydrological dynamics under investigation.

The outcomes of ML also provide data and measurements useful for UC I-3 and UC-4

Display of measured water level from hydrometer network: DT Smart Monitor (I-3)

ML algorithm outcomes such as hydrological data and measured water level available from the hydrometer network could be displayed into the DT Smart Monitor, the SCMS and the AIPo Dashboard, as well. On this purpose a prototype of the user interface structured to show the geographical location of the different sections of the Po River is under development.

Alert functionality for navigability due to hydrological issues (I-4)

Based on the outcomes of ML Algorithm, an alert functionality of the DT for navigation probability forecasting is under development. Different warning level are displayed like a traffic light (not navigable, doubtful, navigable) for the next days. The alert could be provided to the DT Smart Monitor, the SCMS and the AIPo Dashboard as well.

For the execution plan of the DT development please see the WP5 deliverable.

4.2.2. SCMS (developed in WP3)

As regards SCMS, after the indications of the SCMS features of interest in the Italian case, such as the “early detection and info service” the “impact identification service” and the “decision support to action”, the data needed for the SCMS customization to the Padano-Veneto waterway system scenario were discussed and agreed with WP3.

In particular, AIPo with the support of IV, ENEA and UniTra will gather and provide to WP3 the following information:

- Alerts with the respective format: these alerts are the same alerts that AIPo and IV transmit to the skippers today while other data will come from weather forecast sources;
- Padano-Veneto IWW system digital map (including Po River, Fissero-Tartaro-Canalbianco canal, Po-Brondolo canal, Ferrara waterway and some other minor waterways at north of Venice);
- O/D matrices of the goods moved by each of the three main ports along the Po River IWW: port of Cremona, port of Mantua and Port of Rovigo

A detailed execution plan is represented in Figure 18.

Figure 18 SCMS – information collection for its customization to the Italian pilot scenario: execution plan
Source: WP 7 elaboration

4.2.3. Acoustic emissions SHM (developed in WP2 and WP5)

The acoustic emissions (AE) structural health monitoring (SHM) has been developed within WP2 and WP5. The data collected through the AE technology will be processed to predict possible future failures and then display them through the DT (use-case I-6).

In May 2023, CERTH installed the AE sensors on Baricetta lock's doors (May 23-24, 2023) along the Fissero-Tartaro-Canalbianco canal managed by IV and then on Isola Serafini lock's doors (May 25, 2023) along the Po River managed by AIPo and collected data about the health status of the locks' doors (see figure QQ).

The involvement of IV and AIPo is limited to grant the access to the locks for the measurement and received the report of the results (after the elaboration of data in WP 5 - Digital Twin).

Measurements at Isola Serafini lock – AIPo

Measurements at Baricetta lock – Infrastrutture Venete

Figure 19 The set-up of acoustic emissions SHM measurements at Isola Serafini and Baricetta locks

Source: AIPo and IV

Within D2.1 D2.2, CERTH delineates the prototyping efforts of the AE, describing its design and highlighting additional work on its validation and testing using the (present) Italian pilot as well the French one. Comprehensive test results and developments will be encompassed in Task 2.3 and expounded upon in D2.3. Hence, the reader is invited to refer to the related deliverables for the related information on related scheduling and state of play.

4.2.4. Fiber Optic Sensors system (developed in WP2)

The system is being developed within WP2, as part of Task 2.1 Technologies for improving the resilient and reliable navigability, as to allow real-time and continuous monitoring of navigability conditions in free-flowing waterways such as the Po River. To date, the ENEA team has developed and is preparing to test in the laboratory a preliminary prototype of the FOS.

Documentation detailing the conceptual design, operational principles, and the components of the FOS, as well as the development process, can be found in reports D2.1 and D2.2. Hence, the reader is invited to refer to the related deliverables for the related information on related scheduling and state of play.

4.3. Italian pilot Living Lab

According to the description in the Grant Agreement, LL main aim is to provide the framework for the *“strategic development and validation of (the) new solutions (developed in CRISTAL) to increase efficiency, inter-modality, resilience, safety, and security of the transport system, for passengers and freight (through) a sustainable stakeholder partnership among river authorities, policy makers, companies, end-users, non-profit or environmental protection organizations and researchers”* to promote a long term collaboration among them. For the Italian pilot, a specific LLs output is the elaboration of a shared Manifesto for the development of a more resilient competitive and sustainable inland navigation system, with a focus on the “Padano-Veneto” inland waterway system.

The actions undertaken to initiate the Po River Living Lab (LL) in the Italian pilot were carried out in parallel an in agreement with the activities of WP4 activities, particularly those of Task 4.1 and 4.2.

Then, as far as the LL structure, the real-life setting, and the pilot scenario have been depicted according to the Task 4.1 indications. They included:

- Environmental and climate aspects affecting navigation in inland waterways.
- Inland water transport legal and administrative framework, with an analysis of different public authorities (policy makers and administrative authorities) roles, responsibilities and interrelations.
- Physical features of the navigable part of Po River and Fissero–Tartaro–Canalbianco waterway, both natural and infrastructural, including:
 - Assets and their status;
 - Infrastructure bottlenecks;
 - Operational and maintenance activities (dredging, locks maintenance and management, monitoring and water level regulation).
- Economic framework with information about traffic volumes, industrial hubs connected with the waterway, main logistic and navigation operators and their value chain.
- Trade-offs with other water uses such as irrigation, recreation and sport, industry withdrawals and hydraulic safety.

Figure 20 The elements addressed by the Living Lab

Source: Own elaboration

One of the main aspects of real-life setting is represented by the identification of the stakeholders of the IWW transport and logistic system in the “Padano-Veneto” inland waterways system.

To this end, an analysis was driven by the general framework and categorization provided in deliverable D 4.1 (see chapter 2.5 - Table 1), according to which a preliminary stakeholders segmentation was carried out (see chapter 3.3 – Table 6).

Moreover, a direct contractual relationship among them were graphically presented, outlining the complexity of Italian stakeholders' panorama (see chapter 4.3 – figure 6).

In order to reach out to relevant stakeholders of the Italian inland waterways and improve knowledge of the context and dynamics of the transport and logistics system of the “Padano-Veneto” waterways, a specific communication campaign for the Italian case was activated in line with the indications of WP11 from which it emerged that the current governance of the Padano-Veneto inland waterways system was considered one of the main barrier to any IWT development in Italy.

Therefore, as mentioned in chapter 3.2. two objectives were identified for the Italian pilot living labs:

1. To develop a common view on the “Padano-Veneto” waterway governance.
2. To facilitate the acceptance of CRISTAL technologies and systems.

For each objective, a specific cycle of LL has been put in place:

1. The *living lab – cycle governance* with the aim to reach a common view (Manifesto) on the elements that, if solved, could facilitate the development of the Italian IWW.
2. The *living lab – cycle technologies* to collect stakeholders' comments and opinions on the tools/systems considered in the Italian pilot and more in general in CRISTAL Project.

The structure of the Living Lab has been defined as follows:

- Real-life setting elements (pilot scenario);
- Core elements or topics/objectives;
- Principles;
- Scope, especially from a geographic point of view.

This structure is valid for all the LLs regardless of the cycle considered.

According to the quadruple-helix method, stakeholders' groups and the relationships among them have been defined, keeping the inland water transport & logistics system users at the heart (see chapter 3.2)

The stakeholders' matrix and a database of stakeholder contacts were prepared together with a tentative calendar for both type of Living Labs.

An engagement and communication strategy was defined with all the Italian pilot partners and started at the beginning of 2024 with LinkedIn posts, notices in WhatsApp groups and direct invitations to the LLs by email or phone.

It was decided to give priority to the *Living Labs – cycle governance* over the *Living Labs – cycle technologies*, except for the Living Labs related to the cold ironing system which, considering the planned timing of the related activities, have been planned by summer 2024.

Living lab – cycle governance

In this LL cycle, several LLs are planned: first, dedicated LLs with IWW users and with Public Administration involved in the current governance have been arranged and then a final LLs with all the actors will be organized.

The first LL was held on March 15, 2024 (see Figure 21) gathering the needs and the requests of the IWW users. The different issues were categorized by topic and presented and discussed with Public Administrations on April 16, 2024, in a dedicated LL. Then several informal meetings were organized to deepen into each point that emerged in the previous LLs.

The objective is to reach an agreement, a common view (Manifesto), on a list of elements that, if solved, could favour the development of the Italian IWW to be presented to the Italian Ministry of Infrastructures and Transport: a final in-person event to publicly illustrate the "Manifesto" is planned between February and March 2025.

Evento realizzato da:

UNIONTRASPORTI | SOGESCA Sustainable Development

AIPo | Infrastrutture Venete S.r.l.

ENEA

Funded by the European Union

**15 Marzo 2024
ore 14.30-16.00**

ONLINE

Link Zoom
[https://zoom.us/j/99727948210?](https://zoom.us/j/99727948210?pwd=SmIBbUIPUUpXK05kcUljSHNBUysOUT09)
5kcUljSHNBUysOUT09

1° Evento LivingLab USERS Ciclo GOVERNANCE

CRISTAL
CLIMATE, RESILIENT AND ENVIRONMENTALLY SUSTAINABLE TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE, WITH A FOCUS ON INLAND WATERWAYS

Quali sono le problematiche che devi affrontare nell'utilizzo dell'Idrovia?

Quali sono le tue proposte risolutive?

Partecipa all'evento interattivo e ci faremo portavoce delle tue istanze alla pubblica amministrazione e al ministero!

Figure 21 Living lab invitation: 1° LL cycle governance

Source: WP 7 elaboration

Living lab – cycle technologies

As already said, the objective of these LLs is to collect stakeholders' comments and opinions on the tools/systems considered in the Italian pilot and more in general in CRISTAL Project.

In these LLs, after a presentation of the CRISTAL project, the technologies developed in WP2 (FOS, Acoustic Emission), WP3 (SCMS), WP5 (Digital Twin use cases) will be illustrated and discussed in order to collect useful indications for the validation of the respective business models in WP10.

Furthermore, the smart bulletin will be presented and comments and opinions of skippers and IWW transport and logistics operators, i.e. the subjects to whom the bulletin is addressed, will be collected.

These LLs have been planned in the period late 2024 – early 2025, apart from the LLs focused on cold ironing which have already been realized: the first on January 25, 2024, and the second on July 9, 2024.

Figure 22 Living labs: execution plan

Source: WP 7 elaboration

5. Expected Pilot Results & Assessment Plan

In this section the Key Performance Indicators (KPI) selected for the technology/system which will be implemented, although with different degrees of completeness, in the Italian pilot will be illustrated with the description how these KPI will be measured.

Moreover, a first indication about the assessment plan will be outlined together with the innovation plan.

5.1. Expected project key results which are related to the subject matter of the pilot

5.1.1. KPI's of the Italian Pilot

This section outlines the key performance indicators that will be scrutinized to gauge the effectiveness and success of the testing phase.

By meticulously detailing the assessment framework, this chapter lays the foundation for an informed evaluation of the pilot's impact.

Table 4 Italian pilot KPIs for the technology/system developed in WP7

Technology	KPIs	How the KPI will be measured	Measuring data	Base line
Cold ironing	ENV4-NOX (tonnes) [see note ³]	Estimated (feasibility study: overall potential impact of implementing cold ironing)	Data referred to emissions while mooring in the Fissero-Tartaro-CanalBianco waterway	11 tonnes
Cold ironing	ENV5-PM (kg)	Estimated (feasibility study: overall potential impact of implementing cold ironing)	Data referred to emissions while mooring in the Fissero-Tartaro-CanalBianco waterway	233 kg

³ The relevance of the intervention is not just the concentration at a given point (also considering we are not relying on data on a specific location with a sensor) but it is the sum of avoided emissions that could be achieved by a network of equipped berths/mooring points.

Cold ironing	ENV6-GHG as CO ₂ e (tonnes of CO ₂) [see note ⁴]	Estimated (feasibility study: overall potential impact of implementing cold ironing)	Data referred to emissions while mooring in the Fissero-Tartaro-CanalBianco waterway	500 tonnes of CO ₂
Cold ironing	ENV7-Energy consumption (toe)	Estimated (feasibility study of the overall potential impact of implementing cold ironing)	Data referred to energy consumption while mooring in the Fissero-Tartaro-CanalBianco waterway	60 toe
Living Labs - cycle governance	(S1) Number of new or adjusted: - governance models (i.e. governance Manifesto)	Measured	Through the Living Lab, a long-term agreement with all the waterway stakeholders will be set up and the foundations will be laid for a more cohesive and consistent governance framework	0
Forecast model	- solutions (i.e. smart bulletin) - roadmaps and guidelines (i.e. implementation plan)	Measured	The output of the navigability conditions models will be presented in a new smart bulletin	0
Cold ironing		Measured	The cold ironing feasibility study will develop the implementation plan	0
Forecast model	(ITA 4) Navigation forecast points along the river	Test	Number of forecast points	0
Smart bulletin	(S5) Social acceptance survey results (Likert scale)	Test	Questionary/Tests with the involvement of the Living Lab	Not applicable

⁴ If we refer to freight (e.g. choosing an indicator where the emissions are divided by transported tonnes) we are not addressing a "Key" performance indicator since freight transport accounts for only a residual part of potential environmental benefits. Hence, we refer here to the actual consumptions of both passengers and freight units while mooring, which could be saved by implementing the cold ironing. Furthermore, referring to the length of the trip is questionable as well, not only because we are addressing emissions during (long) stops but also because a great part is associated to seasonal storage & maintenance during the wintertime season. In case, see also chapter 6/7 for more details on these specific points.

Smart bulletin	(ITA 2) Navigation bulletin downloads	Test	Counter on AIPo web site/service	20 (today notice to skipper's bulletin)
Smart bulletin	(ITA 3) Registered users	Test	Number of subscriptions (on AIPo platform)	15 (today platform)

Table 5 Italian pilot KPIs developed in other WPs

Technology	KPIs	How the KPI will be measured	Measuring data	Base line
DT Smart Monitor	Users Reservation of Navigation Lock uses case (ITA 1)	Test	Number of reservations (on DT smart monitoring platform use case)	0

5.2. Assessment plan

The results of the pilots will be validated by WP10 in particular under Task 10.3 Pilot Operational Performance versus KPIs and Task 10.4 sustainability validation.

Therefore, the assessment plan will be agreed with the Task 10.3 and Task 10.4 under the coordination of Task 6.4 Analysis and results in the WP 6 - Pilot umbrella.

5.2.1. Innovation plan and expected impact of CRISTAL at the regional and EU level

In the following table (Table 6), the contributions of the technologies (tools/systems) addressed in the Italian pilot to the innovation plan at CRISTAL project level are summarized while Table 7 outlines the contributions of the Italian pilot to the expected impacts of CRISTAL (CRISTAL objectives).

Table 6 Ambition and proposed Innovation

Ambition and proposed Innovation	Technology (developed in CRISTAL)	Reference Partner (WP/Task)
Continuous measurement of water levels in free-flowing waterways	Fiber Optic Sensors (FOS)	ENEA (WP2)
Inform decision making processes towards a disaster resilient management: Decision Support System DSS webGIS platform	Data from “new smart daily report”	AIPo (Task 7.3)
A Corridor Visibility and Open data platform integrated to the synchro-modal corridor management system	Data from “new smart daily report” Potentially, data from cold ironing feasibility study Alert messages: IWW infrastructures status, weather forecasts, ..	AIPo, IV and ENEA (Task 7.3) IV for cold ironing (Task 7.2)
Synchro-modal resource planning and cooperative operations preparation integrated to the synchro-modal corridor management system: A toolbox of services for multimodal planning	Data from “new smart daily report” Potentially, data from cold ironing feasibility study	AIPo, IV and ENEA (Task 7.3) IV for cold ironing (Task 7.2)
Innovative Governance Model	Living Lab approach	SOGESCA (Task 7.4)

Table 7 CRISTAL expected impact

CRISTAL expected impact	Actions planned in the Italian river pilot or related to some of the tasks
<p>Ensure navigability for inland waterways by assuring at least 50% capacity during extreme weather events.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gap analysis (based on guidelines developed by WP3) delivered for selected organizations: 10 companies and 5 public bodies • Provision of some input data (alert) to SCMS developed by WP3 • Provision of navigability condition prediction (based on water level data and hydrometer data) to the DT developed by WP5
<p>Enhance land/sea/infrastructure resilience to extreme weather and human caused events by assuring at least 80% capacity at network level during the disruptions.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provision of some input data (alert) to SCMS developed by WP3 • Provision of navigability conditions predictions (based on water level data and hydrometer data) to the DT developed by WP5
<p>Contribute with at least a 20% increase in modal shift to the sustainability of transport systems.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “New smart daily report to allow better planning of transport operations by logistic operators • Input (smart bulletin or navigability conditions predictions) to SCMS developed by WP3
<p>Ensure resilience and smooth functioning of passenger mobility as well as freight transport and logistics networks operating on these infrastructures.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “New smart daily” report to allow better planning of transport operations by logistic operators • Input (smart bulletin or navigability conditions predictions) to SCMS developed by WP3
<p>Increase the use of recycled materials within or across transport modes by at least 30%.</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Reduce environmental impact (emissions, soil/water pollution, degradation of ecosystems and fragmentation of habitats) during construction, maintenance, operation and decommissioning of the infrastructure in line with the EU environmental legislation.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gap analysis (based on guidelines developed by WP3) delivered to 10 companies and 5 public bodies • Cold ironing possible implementation has the potential to reduce the environmental impact of the transport operations

Development of new governance models that enable cooperation across institutional, modal and national boundaries.

- Through the Living Lab a governance framework based on an agreed “long term collaboration” between the relevant national stakeholders will be outlined (Manifesto).

6. Focusing on Cold ironing – Opportunities, needs and governance framework

This chapter introduces the points of the second part of the present deliverable focusing on the specific theme of cold ironing. To this end, it provides an overview of the opportunities, needs and governance framework representing the context for the feasibility assessment and action plan to be developed. In doing it provides information about both cold ironing per se and the specific context in which its application could be envisaged according to the development strategy and action plan that will be described in the following chapters.

More in particular, the present chapter describes at first the overall framework of cold ironing technology and related infrastructures and how they can support port facilities; then, it provides an overview of known best practices of such technology.

Then, the following paragraphs focus on the starting elements of the study developed by Infrastrutture Venete, including the guidelines for the development of cold ironing on the northern Italy inland waterways and the description of the current situation. To this end, a relevant deal has been paid to the stakeholders identification and involvement through dedicated interviews, which allowed to collect relevant feedback (also supporting the punctual mapping of the landing points and outlining the key needs to be addressed).

6.1. Cold ironing an innovation application for sustainable river ports areas

The term "cold Ironing" refers to the process of supplying shoreside electrical power to nautical units while mooring at berths in ports or other landing places. This solution allows to turn-off onboard (mostly diesel) engines though continuing to cater for the needs of different equipment of a nautical unit, such as emergency equipment, refrigeration, cooling, heating, lighting, etc. Hence, it represents an important measure for the elimination of local pollutants (in the port and in the surrounding areas) and low-frequency noise, produced by the generating sets of nautical units (which propagates over long distances). Cold Ironing is possible through the increase in the electrical infrastructure of the onshore grid serving the nautical units present in the berth. Furthermore, this could be coupled with the implementation of systems powered by renewable energy (e.g. photovoltaic, small wind turbines), thus further improving the environmental sustainability of this solution.

Figure 23 Typical cold ironing structure and its main components.

Source: Aalborg Universitet, A review of the cold ironing technology, Abu Bakar, Nur Najihah; Bazmohammadi, Najmeh; Vasquez, Juan C.; Guerrero, Josep M.

Interventions on the electric grid and energy supply at berths could also be associated with “electric charging” for full electric or hybrid marine units. However, “electric charging” refers to the specific process of charging the batteries of a vessel that is designed to operate in full electric mode or in a hybrid mode (combining electric motors and internal combustion). Full electric units run exclusively on electricity, while hybrids use a combination of electricity and fossil fuels, allowing flexibility and reducing emissions.

In summary, while cold Ironing is a specific method of providing electrical power to marine units in moorings, electric charging refers to a process related to the powering specific marine units designed to exploit the acquired electrical energy especially for their propulsion in the subsequent navigation towards further destinations.

The supply chain for the electrification of docks, Cold Ironing (CI) and Electric Charging (EC), is made up of the following key phases:

- Energy production (also from renewable sources);
- Energy transport;
- Port infrastructure;
- Use of CI and EC services by nautical units.

Figure 24 Cold ironing and electric charging supply chain

Source: Own elaboration

6.2. Best practices at the European level

In order to appropriately develop an effective and innovative approach, capitalising on existing knowledge and state-of-the art at international level, an analysis of best practices at European and international level has been carried out.

First of all, it must be underlined how cold ironing has been developing with particular reference to maritime ports, while fewer examples can be ascertained concerning inland waterways. Nonetheless, relevant ones have been outlined and some particularly relevant examples are briefly summarised here below.

France

In France relevant examples can be ascertained, including various ongoing initiatives carried out by Voies navigables de France (VNF). Among others, the two following examples testify the relevance of the initiatives and commitment with reference to main waterway axes.

A new service for the interactive kiosks for the supply of water and electricity on the Seine axis

To improve its service offering for waterway users, VNF and HAROPA (alliance of the ports of Le Havre, Rouen and Paris) offer a new system of interactive terminals for the supply of water and electricity to river cargo.

This service is part of a sustainable development approach and offers a number of benefits to both shipping companies and local authorities.

In consultation with industry representatives, thirteen kiosks/charging stations have been installed and are now available 24/7 at five sites in the lower Seine. HAROPA and VNF have continued the initiative with

the installation of 67 similar kiosks by 2024 across the Seine River basin. The system provides uniform pricing and the possibility of connecting multiple boats to the same kiosk.

Figure 25 Interventions in the Seine River axis

Source: VNF

River cruises: Electric power terminals on the Rhone in Lyon and the Saône

By the summer of 2025, Voies navigables de France (VNF) will equip the main stopover sites of its network on the Saône and Rhone rivers in Lyon with high-power electrical power supply terminals for liners and hotel ships (vessels of 38.5 metres). Deployed by ENGIE Solutions under a concession agreement, these terminals will distribute low-carbon electricity to cover all of these ships' dockside electricity needs.

The 9 docking points, which will be equipped with 14 electrical terminals (2 sockets per terminal), are located in key points for river navigation on the Saone and Rhone managed by VNF.

In addition to the installation of electric columns, the public service concession also includes the installation of water supply columns for cruise ships and hotel ships to guarantee professionals a safe water supply throughout the journey.

SCE (Saône Confluence Escales) is the sole interlocutor for the management of the service in the busiest sites (Lyon and Chalon-sur-Saône). In fact, SCE will be the only point of contact for the various actors (VNF, local authorities, shipowners and residents) to facilitate exchanges between the various subjects involved in cruise activities, to collect and capitalize on difficulties in quay operations (conflicts of use), to propose ad hoc solutions and to facilitate full use of the terminals through assistance and education.

This service is key to the high potential of the river cruise sector along the Rhône-Saône corridor which has 26 river cruise ships and 110,000 passengers (excluding the COVID crisis period). These cruise ships are between 90 and 135 meters in length, offer 3- or 4-star services and carry on average 150 passengers (from 50 to 190), the majority of customers are European and American. The economic impacts are estimated at 140 million euros for the regions (108 for the regions along the Rhone and 32 for those along the Saone).

This equipment will save approximately 8,500 tonnes of CO₂ emissions per year across the entire network managed by VNF, including 5,800 tonnes in the Greater Lyon area (68% of the total savings).

Netherlands

Connection standard for shore power supply connectors in ports and moorings in the Netherlands

A study of 78 selected ports in the Netherlands with a cargo movement of more than 350 Mtons revealed the following data on the state of the art of the ports regarding cold ironing:

- More than 50% of ports are equipped with between 6 and 10 charging stations.
- About half of the infrastructure present in ports has power ranging from 380 to 32 A.
- More than 70% of ports do not yet have an implementation plan for SSES = Shore-side electricity supply.

There are approximately 16 hardware system suppliers. Moreover, the study addressed thoroughly the technical specifications of the electrical infrastructure.

Germany

Cold ironing pilot project for the inland navigation sector in Germany

The Federal Waterways and Shipping Agency developed a pilot to respond to some current critical issues of the energy supply and electrical infrastructure of ports, namely:

- The existing infrastructure for terrestrial energy is currently insufficient in terms of quantity and quality.
- The payment system (prepaid card) is outdated and not easy to use.
- The poor use of the Agency by customers and the high costs of installation, maintenance and operation negatively impact the quality of the service.

The pilot therefore had the objective of testing new technical standards for cold ironing, analysing and evaluating the costs for the installation and operation of this system, and increasing customers and electricity sales.

The pilot was set up in 20 ports in the western German canal network, where around 120 connections are being renewed or newly built, and in one port on the Rhine.

Moreover, it included experimenting with two types of elements: the electrical junction boxes (see the following figure) and flexible payment systems.

First pilot results can be summarised as follows.

- Junction boxes:
 - "Made-to-measure" junction boxes have the advantage of being optimally adapted to the needs of the customers and the operators and to comply with legal requirements without fail. During design and construction, national regulations, such as standards and calibration rules, must be respected.
 - The calibration process was complex and time consuming.
 - The qualitative creation of the units required an interactive process between the client and the contractor, which was time consuming, and this meant that the development of the final unit took an extremely long time.
- Payment systems:
 - Modern payment systems can be booked on the market.
 - Invoicing has a significant cost (Claim-Management, etc.).
 - Accurate billing in kilowatt hours carries legal consequences.
 - The backend and frontend system are very complex and requires specific knowledge for assignment and technical support.

Figure 26 An example of the junction boxes developed in the pilot

Source: Federal Waterways and Shipping Administration

Next steps and considerations:

- In the coming years the Agency intends to massively expand its range of connections to cold ironing.
- The old system can no longer be maintained.
- The Agency's working group dedicated to cold ironing is developing a system at national level based on the results of the pilot project.
- Various possible solutions for hardware, backend and operation as well as pricing (e.g. subscriptions or precise kWh) and authorization are currently being discussed.

River ports of the city of Bremen

Within the Horizon 2020 project IW-NET, the case study of the ports of the city of Bremen focused on the topic of digitalization of the docks and solutions for shore power.

The current situation, the consequences and the pilot projects tested in the field to find efficient solutions to the critical issues encountered in the current condition are summarized below.

The main actors involved in the pilot activities were river transport operators, port traffic coordinators and managers of port infrastructure and services.

The pilot actions fundamentally focused on testing an efficient infrastructure management system within the "Internet of Things": the IW-NET shore power solution. This system is able to:

- Control of access to the port and detection of their closure status.
- Recording and transmission of electricity meter readings.
- Communication with external systems via web interfaces.

Therefore, it was opted for a management system tailored to specific needs and not "ready to use" because:

- It was necessary to find an economical retrofit and connection solution for existing systems.
- The direct connection between port management and port access authorization would have allowed use and invoicing without additional payment systems.
- Complete control of the communication network would have allowed additional sensors to be easily integrated.

Austria

FAIRway works! in the Rhine-Danube corridor

The most relevant activity of the FAIRway works! Project (co-financed by the co-financed by the Connecting Europe Facility - CEF Programme) related to cold ironing is the strengthening of the infrastructure of public mooring places along the Austrian Danube, i.e. the 3 mooring points: Linz, Wildungsmauer and Vienna shown in the following figure

Figure 27 Interventions in the Danube River

Source: "FAIRway works! in the Rhine-Danube Corridor" project (CEF Programme)

In this way it is intended to contribute to the development of an energy self-sufficient waterway: Installation of a cold ironing system in Austria by Viadonau (Austrian Shipping Company Ltd., founded in 2005 by the Federal Ministry for Climate Action, Environment, Energy, Mobility, Innovation and Technology) which in 2019 developed a strategy for 2030 in relation to the reduction of environmental impacts, the efficiency of mobility and environmental protection for its services, aligned with the main European strategies and directives.

Among the measures envisaged, the Austrian company has also produced guidelines for planning cold ironing in all the federal states involved, through the study of case studies relating to the following three typologies, namely:

- 1) Cruise ships in private moorings;
- 2) Cruise ships during the winter stopover in ports;
- 3) Cargo ships in public moorings.

The drafting of the guidelines was conducted through a working group made up of ViaDonau network managers, energy suppliers, mooring and port operators, and representatives of the federal states and also stakeholders from Bavaria. The guidelines therefore include technical specifications regarding shore power units, analysis, cost and profitability estimates and considerations on organizational concepts (including the access and billing system).

An interesting aspect regarding cost sustainability was highlighted by an interview in 2021 conducted by a due diligence in the context of the development of the guidelines, i.e. that subsidies are needed to make cold ironing projects economically sustainable.

European Federation of River Ports

Challenges and lessons from a port perspective on cold ironing/On Power Supply (OPS)

The current challenges that the sector must approach from an infrastructure point of view are:

- Lack of clarity of the sector's needs;
- Lack of a successful business model;
- Lack of suppliers;
- Lack of local funding;
- Little awareness of the importance of this system among managers;
- Lack of harmonisation.

While the challenges from the users' point of view are:

- Short mooring times (8 hours or less) which do not encourage investments;
- Lack of obligations in using the OPS;
- Renewal of old fleets to adapt them to new standards;
- Need for territorial planning.

On the contrary, the main opportunities in the sector are:

- Possibility of harmonizing the existing infrastructure given its lack of homogeneity;
- The incentives offered by CEF projects;
- Cooperation of stakeholders along shipping corridors, especially in countries such as Holland, France and Germany;
- Support through national policies;
- The success of case studies on cruises.

Other good practices

Among key references there are the manual “*Collection of examples and lessons learned on mooring requirements and necessary equipment*” produced by the CCNR - Central Commission for the Navigation of the Rhine, which defines technical elements of executive design of the cold ironing systems, and the EALING PROJECT (European flagship action for cold ironing in ports) co-financed by the CEF programme. The latter, although focused on maritime transport, contains an excellent analysis and a series of recommendations in reference to the main regulatory instruments, the technical, environmental and economic characteristics of the cold ironing system.

The following table presents a brief overview of the best practices and initiatives described above.

Table 8 Summary of presented best practices

Country/organization	Project/initiative	Brief description
France	Voies Navigables de France (VNF) Kiosks	Installation of electric kiosks along the Seine River, providing 24/7 shore power to reduce emissions from idling engines for cargo vessels. Planned expansion to Rhône and Saône rivers for cruise ships and floating hotels.
The Netherlands	Dutch Port Shore Power Study	Survey of 78 ports revealed over half have shore power stations, with a need for consistent implementation plans and cross-border standards.
Germany	Federal Waterways Shore Power Modernization	Over 120 shore power connections upgraded to support diverse vessel types, with pilot programs testing payment solutions and flexible connection standards.
Austria	Pilot by Viadonau within FAIRway works! Project (CEF Programme)	Focuses on energy self-sufficiency along the Danube, encouraging ports to offer renewable energy for sustainable shipping and supporting EU Green Deal goals.
European Federation of River Ports	River Port Standardization Efforts	Addresses barriers to adoption like funding and standardization, with opportunities to access CEF funding and collaborate with neighbouring countries.

Other EU/international initiatives	EALING Project and CCNR Guidelines	Provides regulatory, technical, and operational guidelines for implementing cold ironing across Europe, aiming for harmonization and support for smaller ports.
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6.3. Minimum standards for Cold Ironing in relation to inland navigation systems

A key input and guidelines for the development of cold ironing on the northern Italy inland waterways is provided by Infrastrutture Venete in 2022 and approved by the administrations and bodies involved in “Interregional agreement for navigation on the river Po⁵”.

Their relevance is also given to the fact that in Italy, to date, the technical elements related to the electrical connection systems between the quay and the nautical units of inland navigation have not yet been defined, as these involve technologies and needs that are completely different from those of maritime navigation.

Considering all the possible types of nautical units that navigate on the national waterway system, from internal regional networks to interregional networks up to CEMT class V, taking into account the existing infrastructures which limit the maximum size of nautical units to those measuring 110 m x 11.40 m with a maximum draft of up to 3.50 metres, it is possible to identify the following families of nautical units:

Pleasure craft (including houseboats): nautical units intended for navigation for sporting or tourist/recreational purposes, motorized, suitable for navigation in shallow waters, especially inland waters, of variable dimensions (average dimensions approximately 12 m x 5 m). In particular, the houseboat is represented as a small river yacht, equipped with a flat bottom and a comfortable habitable cabin. When the pleasure boat is docked at the dock it requires electricity for some services including air conditioning, heat pump, induction cooking points, battery power for bilge pumps.

Medium-sized tourist ships (approximately 40 m x 8 m with draft of 1 – 1.50 m and draft of 4 m) for transport and river cruises of up to 40 passengers (examples are the Vita Pugna, Ave Maria boats and Mary).

Large tourism ships (approximately 110 m x 11.40 m with 3 decks) used for river cruises for up to 150-170 passengers (examples are the Michelangelo and Venezia boats).

Commercial tugboats/pushers for the transport of goods on river barges: these are nautical vehicles used for moving barges (pushing and/or accompanying) for the transport of goods up to 1,500 – 2,000 tons each (examples include those of the Fagioli company). Inside the tug/pusher, in addition to the control panel and the engines, there is usually also a cabin for the crew.

⁵ See chapter 2

Description of the electrical power systems of the nautical units

For each family of nautical units described above, the technical specifications necessary to guarantee their operation on the dock with exclusive electrical power will be listed below. The type of electrical sockets described below takes into account the possibility of completely turning off the fossil fuel engines of the nautical units while they are stationed at the dock.

Pleasure crafts (including houseboats)

This type of nautical unit requires 16-32 A CEE electrical sockets powered at 230 V up to a power of 6-7 kW. These nautical units are equipped with a 12 V -220 V inverter transformer on board.

Medium-sized tourist ships

This type of nautical unit requires sockets powered at 400 V with an intensity of 63 A, 5 poles (3 phases + Neutral + Earth) up to approximately 41 kW of power.

Large tourist ships used for river cruises

This type of nautical unit, with all services turned on and functioning, requires one/two 5-pole 400 V sockets (3 phases + Neutral + Earth) with an intensity of 125 A up to approximately 82 kW of power.

As an alternative to this type of socket, it would be useful to set up a power lock with separate cords (i.e. with all phases separate + Neutral + Earth also separated) as already happens in Northern Europe and very useful in cases of absorption exceeding 80 kW. In this case the power lock with separate strings should have the following characteristics:

- 400V;
- up to 400 A;
- up to approximately 263 kW.

This power lock is more easily adaptable to a larger number of nautical units and allows solving the problem of the electrical pick-up of air conditioning systems which can reach up to 300 A for this type of ship.

When this type of nautical unit is stopped at the dock in the winter period, even for a few months for maintenance, consumption is limited to a maximum of 80 kW.

Commercial tugboats/pushers for transporting goods on river barges

This type of nautical unit, unlike the others previously described, moored in the port for a limited duration of a few hours or a maximum of 1-2 days (including the night). It does not require a lot of power as energy consumption is strictly related to the consumption of the cabin for the staff and for the management of the control panel.

This type of nautical vehicle requires sockets powered at 400 V up to 20 kW and 63 A intensity with 5 poles (3 phases + Neutral + Earth). However, there are older tugboats/pushers that require the same 4-pole sockets (3 phases + Earth).

Further elements related to the requirements arising matching of the needs of the different nautical units making use of a specific typology landing points will be described in the following chapter 8.4.

6.4. Governance & Stakeholders involvement

For the specific purpose of the present activity related to cold ironing, a particular subset of the overall stakeholders interested in IWW was targeted and then involved with dedicated workshops and bilateral exchanges, though framed within the overall CRISTAL project activity.

In particular, this subset is composed by owners and managers of landing points and economic operators involved in the passengers and freight transport. The owners and managers mainly include local public administrations and infrastructure operators including AIPO and Infrastrutture Venete themselves.

6.4.1. Stakeholders interviews – summary and key takeaways

In practice, stakeholder involvement was essentially conducted in 3 steps: launch event, bilateral interviews and the final event:

- **Launch event.** After the recognition, mapping and selection, the main stakeholders of the project were invited to the launch event of the study held online on 25 January 2024.
- **Bilateral interviews.** Subsequently, both the participants of the launch event and most of the identified stakeholders were contacted for bilateral interviews. Through the support of digital mapping and a detailed questionnaire (see attachments), all the information necessary to identify the main elements of the main landing places, services and infrastructures was collected to reason about the proposal of interventions to be carried out for the implementation of cold ironing. From January 2024 to June 2024, more than 30 interviews were conducted with the authorities responsible for the landing places, the service operators, both tourist transport and energy, detailed in the attached chapters "Stakeholder involvement and participatory process".
- **Final event.** On 09 July 2024, the current state of the mapping of the landing places and related equipment was presented, also with reference to the needs of the different types of nautical units, and a first proposal for the implementation of a cold ironing system in the managed waterway network by Infrastrutture Venete. The meeting was also an opportunity to verify, with the stakeholders, the elements proposed also with a view to designing an integrated system, including other synergistic elements, such as the possibility of charging from the dock for both hybrid and electric nautical units.

On the basis of the collected data and matching them with other statistics, it has possible to assess the fuel consumption while mooring at berths in ports or other landing places, which could be avoided by implementing the cold ironing solution.

Taking into account all the different nautical units and typologies of traffic (i.e., both passenger and freight) and making reference to the Fissero-Tartaro-Canalbianco waterway, about 185,000 litres on a yearly basis could be saved.

The following pie chart, showing the percentual makeup of all the different component, highlights the limited values associated to freight transport (accounting for less than 1% of the grand total), while cruises

are associated with more than 95%. It is worth noting that a relevant part of these consumptions is associated to seasonal storage and maintenance during the winter season.

Obviously, these values are related to the current flows and the specific conditions of the addressed waterway. In this regard, we can envisage also a certain increase in the volumes, especially for certain typologies (e.g. in particular freight and large cruise ships) after the removal of relevant bottlenecks and other envisaged interventions.

Nonetheless the general remark on the limited value associated to freight transport is inherent to the limited power need of the related units used in the concerned IWW, as already described in the previous 6.3 chapter.

Figure 28 Breakdown in different categories of the fuel consumption at berths in the Fissero-Tartaro-Canalbianco waterway

Source: Own elaboration

6.5. Mapping and identification of existing landing points

In order to provide a comprehensive understanding of the state-of-play, all the landing points located along Fissero-Tartaro waterway have been mapped.

Moreover, to ensure a greater overall vision and to be able to describe the whole territorial framework of reference, the Litoranea Veneta waterways were mapped and also some landing places located along further rivers and/or areas (River Po; River Mincio and River Sile), which emerged as potential strategic points from the dialogue with the public and private stakeholders who were interviewed.

For each landing place, an exhaustive form was compiled with data relating to:

- The owner/manager body and related contacts;
- Characteristics including available facilities and services;
- Relevant interconnections and notes;
- The usage and related traffic flows.

Figure 29 Mapping of the landing places

Source: Own elaborations

7. Cold ironing development strategy

This chapter focuses on the development strategy devised to foster the deployment of cold ironing in the Italian context.

Starting from the long-term vision that lays the foundation and objectives of the strategy itself, the following sections outline different scenarios that are being considered in the subsequent assessment of feasibility. Lastly, the main elements that influence the level of potential feasibility are described, stemming from the financial and technical levels to the environmental scope.

7.1. Long-term vision and strategy

The analysis of the state of the art, the interviews with the operators and those responsible for the nodes along the IWW have made it possible to arrive, through the first phase of qualitative and quantitative analysis and a participatory path, at the definition of a vision for an intervention plan for a cold ironing system.

Figure 30 Definition of the comprehensive strategic approach

Source: Own elaboration

This will then be the basis for defining the interventions in the Implementation Plan. In this way, it is possible to develop an overall model, which can be replicated in other contexts. In order to be comprehensive and long-standing the overall vision encompasses not only cold ironing but also electric charging and is referred to the three waterway axes managed by Infrastrutture Venete:

1. Fissero-Tartaro-Canalbianco-Po di Levante ;
2. Po-Brondolo;
3. Litoranea Veneta.

Though the main focus of this analysis (especially in the short-medium term) is represented by the first two axes, the third one represents a relevant example to be taken into account also in relation to a more general vision that includes a further extension to other minor waterways, interested by tourism-related and recreational trips though not suitable for freight transport.

7.2. Scenario hypotheses

When considering the potential interventions on the basis of the vision, both the complex system of the three waterway axes and the specific aspects and characteristics of each node and landing place have to be considered. This calls for an operational approach encompassing the following 4 scenarios:

- The *initial scenario*: it is the initial situation, without cold ironing facilities.
- The *business as usual/already ongoing interventions scenario*: this scenario includes the currently ongoing intervention for equipping with cold ironing only the node of Rovigo Interporto.
- The *positive scenario*: an essential intervention to guarantee the minimum equipment for the electrification on selected landing points but allowing a functional coverage of the Fissero-Tartaro-Canalbianco waterway.
- The *optimal scenario*: the infrastructural state of existing services and mobility for the whole system, will be enhanced encompassing both cold ironing and electric charging.

Therefore, scenarios are stemming from a basic to a complex and interconnected ecosystem where a multitude of factors are contributing to the success of the electrification of the docks, taking into account the complexity of services, peculiarities of the places and needs of the different managers, operators and users who gravitate around the different landing places.

Moreover, such scenarios are considering the future developments of the following 4 clusters representing the waterway system in its complexity:

- **The type of nautical units.**
This cluster includes the types of vessels in service in the auctions covered by the study that transit, land and refuel in the various ports, depending on the service provided, passengers or goods. The types of boats are therefore:
 - Pleasure craft (including houseboats);
 - Medium-sized tourist ships (e.g. motor ships);
 - Large tourist ships used for river cruises;
 - Commercial tugboats/pushers for transporting goods on river barges.
- **The type of service**
The service could be aimed at:
 - Tourist (cruise ships, motor ships for regular or occasional services by specialized operators with even prolonged overnight stops and disembarkation and embarkation of people);
 - Recreational (medium or small sized pleasure craft with permanent mooring or occasional mooring);
 - Commercial (tugboats and barges for cargo handling activities).

- **The landing typology.**

This cluster includes the different types of landing places i.e.:

- Dock, typically in reinforced concrete;
- Floating wooden dock;
- Wooden pier on piles.

The different landing places are also identified according to the presence or absence of sub-services (e.g. electricity, lighting, drinking water), services (e.g. fuel supply, toilets), and the presence of new projects both during construction and in the project (e.g. redevelopment interventions, expansion, etc.).

- **The rear-landing system.**

This cluster includes services linked to the mobility and intermodality of the various landing places (e.g. tri-modal rail-road-water nodes), the types of landing place managers (directly from Infrastrutture Venete, public and/or private concessionaires, premises), services and attraction centres for the tourism sector (e.g. interregional cycle paths, museums, natural parks).

7.3. Assessing the feasibility from the technical and economical viewpoints

Taking into account the hypotheses described in the scenarios (which were then the reference on which the action plan reported in the following chapter has been developed) as well as the minimum requirements associated with (resulting in specific set of installation that will be further clarified in par. 8.3), a preliminary assessment leads to the following costs associated to each scenario.

The prices for the installation of each unit were hypothesized on the basis of the first market references currently being verified, awaiting definitive offers from potential suppliers and installers. These unit amounts were then multiplied by the assumed units to obtain a total budget, which is to be verified and fine-tuned through the next implementation stages of the system as it is strongly affected by auxiliary interventions (which are being further detailed in the following steps including the design of typical plant).

Moreover, a great part of the costs is also related to other complementary interventions (i.e. addressing the Litoranea Veneta and also the installations for the electric charge), in addition to the primary objective of cold ironing in the Fissero-Tartaro-Canalbianco waterway. However, it is important to take them into account as well in the strategic approach to avoid partial interventions. Even from the practical point-of-view, it is important to avoid spot interventions in order to allow users to carry out trips making use of the same approach. Moreover, it is to consider the opportunity to carry out interventions in a given location at once or at least according to a coherent and coordinated approach.

7.3.1. Focus on environmental impacts

The following elements of sustainability and circularity, energy, environmental and social indicators are to be highlighted related to both the cold ironing (CI) and electric charge (EC).

1. Determination of the energy supply (kWh) of the proposed solutions, encompassing both CI and EC.

Again, with reference to the proposed interventions, the use of the applied solutions (CI and EC) was hypothesized in terms of kWh supplied. The calculation was carried out starting from the following assumptions:

- i. The equipment will supply energy to vessels with different absorption capacities. As first hypothesis, the average energy delivered was estimated equal to approximately 60% of the point was evaluated, for approximately 14% of hourly use over the annual hours as a weighted average between seasonality and operating methods of the tourism, recreational and industrial sectors.
- ii. Based on these indicators, the quantity of energy supplied per year was calculated for each individual type of equipment.
- iii. The energy supplied was applied to the amount of equipment installed for each landing place and for each phase.
- iv. Finally, to calculate the quantity potentially supplied.

Total (preliminary) estimate, for the optimal scenario (taking into account all possible interventions): 7,764 MWh potentially supplied on yearly basis at the end of the development process.

2. Estimated diesel saved (liters) (CI plus EC).

The equivalent of liters of diesel fuel saved was calculated starting from the l/kWh equivalence identified by the analysis of the sizing and capacity of the batteries: 3.88 kWh/l, which is equivalent to 0.2577 l/kWh. The obtained unit quantities of saved consumption were applied to the installations for the different phases.

Total (preliminary) estimate: indicatively 2 million litres of diesel fuel potentially saved on a yearly basis at the end of the development process.

3. Identification of average emissions (CI plus EC).

The identification of the average emissions for each liter of diesel fuel in a marine engine was carried out through the comparison of different sources and studies, for the main air pollutants and greenhouse gases. The values are in some cases expressed as "average" because:

- NO_x (Nitrogen Oxides) emissions can vary significantly depending on the emission control technology present in the engine;
- Literature values vary from approximately 0.5 to 2 g/L regarding PM (particles and fine dust):
- Literature values vary from approximately 1 to 2 g/L as regards VOC (Volatile Organic Compounds).
- Literature values regarding SO₂ (Sulfur Dioxide) vary from approximately 2 to 20 g/L. The value depends on the sulfur content of the diesel fuel, which is generally higher in marine diesel fuels.

The identification of the average emissions for each kWh of electricity produced was carried out using the average CO₂ data per kWh from the national energy mix (250 g/kWh), reported by

various GSE⁶ reports, integrated with ISPRA⁷ data. The same sources propose reference values for air polluting emissions. It should be underlined that these values represent a first preliminary estimation based on available data. Moreover, these are constantly evolving thanks to the diffusion of solutions for the production of energy from renewable sources which benefit the energy mix with the consequent progressive reduction of the related emissions. In addition to this, the potential deriving from possible micro-grid installations for the self-production of green energy on site must also be taken into account.

With regard to this last element, it is important to underline that the study hopes that the electrification of the docks can rely on the local production of green energy, whether this is produced on a punctual level through micro-grids or whether it is produced within wider territorial contexts, as in the case of energy communities.

Some isolated experiences also emerged from the interviews with the port managers: this is the case of Mantua where there is an energy community based on the production of hydrogen (H2 Valley) and the case of the Rovigo interporto where a photovoltaic system will be installed in the Commercial Port.

The local production of green energy is an optimal solution, especially in highly industrialized/populated areas, where the development of circular/sustainable energy production and use systems can be envisaged, taking into consideration that in the Po Valley area, and within geographical area affected by the study, energy production via photovoltaic and agri-photovoltaic (also called “agrivoltaic”) systems are more suitable solutions than energy production via micro-wind power, for obvious reasons of resource availability. These solutions are recommended but not binding.

In this regard, it is to highlight relevant initiatives and incentives testify a growing interest and commitment towards green energy production models. Among others, it is to mention the opportunities related to the Regional Law of Veneto No. 17 of July 19, 2022. In fact, it establishes the regulatory framework for agrivoltaics, promoting the development of photovoltaic systems that coexist with farming practices, aiming to optimize land use while preserving agricultural productivity. To this end, it sets guidelines for sustainable installation, ensuring that agrivoltaic projects do not negatively impact soil quality, landscape, or biodiversity. By offering incentives and clear regulations, it aims to foster investment to support both energy transition and rural economic development.

⁶ GSE S.p.A. (Gestore dei Servizi Energetici) is the Italian Energy Services Operator, which periodically publishes data and statistics on the renewable sources used in Italy.

⁷ ISPRA (Istituto superiore per la protezione e la ricerca ambientale) is the Italian Institute for Environmental Protection and Research.

8. Cold Ironing Action Plan and recommendations

In this chapter a brief description of the key elements to be addressed to pave the way for an actual and successful implementation of the strategic vision is provided.

8.1. The Action Plan approach

The present paragraph outlines the Action Plan that is proposed as a key takeaway from the analyses and surveys described in the previous chapter. In order to appropriately accompany the design, realisation and implementation of the cold ironing system an overall process is to be carried out.

To this end, an action plan is meant to support the development of the cold ironing according to a stepwise and adaptative and participatory approach. In fact, this includes several aspects in addition to the mere infrastructural realisation. In particular, this includes all the actions related to ensuring an adaptative and participatory approach to be carried through (and partly, depending to) the active participation and commitment of different public and private stakeholders. They shall represent different levels and roles, including infrastructure owners involved in the realisation phase, as well as market players willing to be involved in the management and provision of the energy supply and final users.

Along with relevant cost and associated financing needs, the need for a consensus building process (starting from the vision and technical elements and mapping activity resulted from the present analysis), should be considered as well. This follow-up process should iteratively fine-tune the estimation and activate specific part of the overall set of interventions making up the whole development strategy described in the previous chapter.

In this regard it is important to outline relevant points, which should provide methodological guidelines to be further specified with reference to the activation of each part of the system development process:

- Ensuring the active participation of all the needed stakeholders taking into account the need for a well-coordinated multilevel governance (possibly, including partnership between public and public actors) and possible different scheme in the actual management of the landing points and related services to the users;
- Unlocking potentials from synergic interventions looking as regards to both intermodal transport and sustainable tourism promotion as well as renewable energy production;
- Facilitating the intervention by ensuring funding for the infrastructure realisation, exploiting possible financing opportunities, and smooth administrative procedures and, in case, providing incentives to users;
- Fine-tuning of design and keeping track of new opportunities that could arise from technological innovations;
- Accompanying the implementation with supportive activities as monitoring, communication and training of operators.

8.2. Steps of implementation of the Action Plan

In this paragraph an ideal sequence of steps is presented, as described in the first paragraph of this chapter, the actual implementation stages will be further defined and updated during the development of the participatory process.

- **Phase 0 – “Interporto di Rovigo – state of play in 2024”**

This step is represented only by the intervention in the Rovigo intermodal logistic node. In fact, as seen in the previous chapters, the Rovigo interporto is interested, in the current state of writing of this report (June 2024) by an executive project under construction for electrification interventions on the docks of the commercial port together with ancillary interventions such as integration of lighting, fire prevention systems, photovoltaics, etc.

It is therefore defined as the first step already in the implementation phase, and therefore also as a reference model, for the electrification of waterways, the subject of this study. It corresponds to the “Business as usual Scenario”.

- **Phase 1 – “ready to go” in 2025**

The interventions relating to the so-called priority landing places is representing the second step to be accomplished, in which in the short and medium term it will be possible to proceed with the electrification of the docks with relatively limited investments. This will be possible because these nodes already have an excellent level of infrastructure (both sub-services and services), have a high transport flow of both goods and passengers, are subject to stopover and refuelling of tourist and commercial boats and enjoy a good level of intermodality (railway, road and waterborne).

In this case the moorings will satisfy the minimum needs with respect to the cold ironing of boats already in operation with columns of 82-20 kW of power. It corresponds to a first set of interventions belonging to the “Positive Scenario”.

- **Phase 2 – “fast followers” in 2026-27**

The following step encompasses the development of the so-called intermediate landing places (at the level of intervention priority and not landing size), in which in the medium term with relatively limited investments, but higher than in phase 1, it will be possible to proceed with the electrification of the docks, satisfying all the cold ironing power needs of nautical units, even the largest (such as the Michelangelo cruise ship). These landing places are complementary to those already present in phase 1 and sometimes do not yet have any subservices at present. It corresponds to a second set of interventions leading to the completion of the “Positive Scenario”.

Phase 3 – “Future projects” in 2030

A further step is then represented by the future projects encompassing the completion of interventions activated with Phase 2 with the installation of charging columns for full electric boats (EVSE) and which, therefore, will be completed with the installation of charging columns of 22, 200, 400 up to 1000 kW of power, in a future scenario in which all electric boats will be able to navigate

in complete autonomy in all 3 waterway axes taken into consideration in this study. It corresponds to a first set of interventions belonging to the “Optimal Scenario”.

- **Phase 4 – “Full electric” after 2030**

A last step is then represented by the full electrification of the IWW allowing all boats to be electrically propelled if economic and infrastructural conditions allow it. It corresponds to a second set of interventions leading to the completion of the “Optimal Scenario”.

Summary map of Action Plan proposed steps

Below is a summary representation of the waterway axes with the location of the landing places addressed by the development phases proposed. The colouring of the dots referring to the phases of the scenarios described above. Obviously, the list of intervention will be further consolidated also on the basis of the fine-tuned estimation of costs to be carried out while finalising the feasibility study.

Figure 31 Location of the interventions Fissero Tartaro Canalbianco Po di Levante waterway
Source: Own elaboration

Figure 32 Location of the interventions Po – Brondolo waterway

Source: Own elaboration

8.3. Recommendations for a Monitoring Plan and Communication activities

The first point relates to the need of monitoring through quantitative elements the development and effects of the carried-out interventions, as to be in condition (if needed) to carry out the needed adjustments. These adjustments could be related to relevant margin of uncertainty also related to difficulty of making assumptions on the evolution of the demand as well as on possible future technological developments, etc.

To this end, a possible monitoring plan should be based on the systematic collection of data on a regular basis, starting from further consolidating the knowledge about the actual demand. Then, especially, the implementation and realisation of intervention, a key task will be associated to the effective and continuous monitoring of their utilization level.

Another key success-factor of the present initiative is related to active and synergic involvement and contribution of a vast and heterogenous set of decision-makers and stakeholders up to the final users.

In this regard, special attention should be paid to thorough and regular communication activities, which also include practical aspects such as operational instructions to users.

8.4. Input for designing typologies of cold-ironing interventions

In compliance with the minimum standards set in the guidelines introduced in chapter 6.3, a set of minimum requirements, to be taken into account as input for different typologies of landing points, are provided in this paragraph.

In particular, these requirements are specifically referred to the following typologies of landing points:

- **Tourist port:** a tourist port is defined as that particular type of port infrastructure built or dedicated to purely recreational use. It can be equipped with facilities for the storage, repair and refuelling of vessels.
- **Docking piers** positioned along the river banks: they are bridges of various lengths, generally made up of a scaffold supported by metal or wooden or reinforced concrete poles, which is built starting from the bank towards greater depths, to allow the docking to vessels (movement of materials, transit of people, refuelling of ships, unloading of crude oil from tankers, etc.) along the river banks. They are usually made of wood, sometimes even floating, and without infrastructure and services in the surrounding areas.
- **Port quays:** these are the parts of the port facing the water that allow ships or vessels to safely approach the mainland and secure them in such a way as to allow the embarkation and disembarkation of people or the loading and unloading of goods.

Minimum standards for cold ironing by type of landing point

For each one of the above-described typologies the following minimum standards for cold ironing are indicated:

- **Tourist port:** in tourist ports equipped with piers for small nautical units (e.g. pleasure craft and houseboats), preference should be given to single 230 V columns each with 16-32A CEE sockets with a maximum power of approximately 7 kW (the number of the columns varies according to the size of the marina).
- **Docking piers** positioned along the river banks: in this type of landing place, the mixed presence of both 230 V columns each with CEE sockets with a maximum power of 6-7 kW (for use by pleasure craft) and columns would be useful 400 V each with 63 A 5-pole sockets (3 phases + Neutral + Earth) with a maximum power of approximately 41 kW (for use by medium-sized tourist ships). The number of columns varies according to the size of the marina.
- **Port quays:** in this case the plant offering must be as varied as possible for all types of nautical units. The number of connection columns must be distributed homogeneously along the entire available length of the docks considering a distance between centres of approximately 100-120 meters (taking into account longer boats). It is a good idea for each workstation to be equipped with at least:
 - two 230 V CEE sockets with a maximum power of 6-7 kW;
 - a 400V - 63 A – max 41 kW 5-pole socket;
 - two 400V – 125 A – max 82 kW 5-pole sockets.

It is also a good idea for at least half of the columns on each port quay to be equipped with a power lock with separate cords with the following technical characteristics:

- 400V;
- up to 400 A;
- up to approximately 263 kW.

The above definition takes into account the various possible uses of cold ironing depending on the type of nautical unit, its permanence in the port and the seasonality which strongly influences energy

consumption related to air conditioning. For the sizing of the electrical system, it is possible to consider the simultaneous use of the two 230V CEE sockets with the 400 A power lock, as the use of the two 125 A sockets (or the single 63 A socket) can be considered an alternative to that of the 400 A power lock.

As required by Annex 709B of the CEI 64-8 standard, it is also advisable that appropriate instructions for use of the systems to be posted on the dock. However, it is useful for the manager of the cold ironing systems to provide suitable instructions to the nautical unit staff when docking at the dock.

Furthermore, when the nautical unit is stationed at the dock, in addition to the electrical power necessary to reduce pollution as previously described, it requires these additional services:

- LED lighting to operate in the column area;
- Drinking water supply (UNI 45 compatible with the flow rate of the water system);
- Possibility of discharging wastewater into the gray and black water sewer system.

Therefore, it would be useful to equip the columns dedicated to cold ironing with these services as well.

9. Conclusions

Starting from a description of the context and challenges of the Padano Veneto waterway system, the present deliverable has presented in detail the main objectives of Italian River Pilot that are:

- To increase the reliability of the IWW;
- To improve the sustainability;
- To make the preventive maintenance of locks and the riverbed more effective.

All the objectives are linked to the CRISTAL global objectives which are to improve the reliability of IWW transportation and increase its share in the different transport modes.

To achieve the first objective, a navigability conditions prediction model and a smart bulletin will be directly developed in the pilot while some use-cases of the Digital Twin (DT) and some features of Synchronic Corridor Management System (SCMS) will be customized, respectively by WP5 and WP3, on the basis of the Italian IWW.

As far as the sustainability objective is concerned, a detailed study for the implementation of cold ironing systems in the quays along the Fissero-Tartaro-Canalbianco-Po di Levante has been developed and further deepening is ongoing. This solution, has been particularly focused on in the present deliverable, also outlining a related action plan. Moreover, a GAP analysis of the compliance with the climate change mitigation and adaptation international standards and EU policy of the organizational model of some IWW stakeholders will be carried out.

The last objective related to predictive maintenance will be achieved through an initial evaluation of the effectiveness of acoustic emission technology for assessing the good condition of lock's doors (see WP2 and WP5) and with the development of a prototype of a fiber optic sensor system to monitor the accumulation of debris on the riverbed (see WP2).

Furthermore, for each proposed tool/solution the activities carried out so far have been described with the overall execution plan.

Finally, for each technology/system developed entirely within the Italian pilot project, the baseline of the related KPIs and their respective relationships with the project objectives were indicated.

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11. List of tables

Table 1 Alignment of D7.1 contents to the corresponding GA deliverable & task(s) descriptions.....	9
Table 2 Annual Transported goods in the Padano-Veneto waterway system – year 2021.	21
Table 3 Pilot’s stakeholders’ classification	24
Table 4 Italian pilot KPIs for the technology/system developed in WP7	52
Table 5 Italian pilot KPIs developed in other WPs.....	54
Table 6 Ambition and proposed Innovation.....	55
Table 7 CRISTAL expected impact.....	56
Table 8 Summary of presented best practices.....	66

12. List of figures

Figure 1 The Padano Veneto waterway system	14
Figure 2 The Padano-Veneto waterways system within the core and comprehensive TEN-T network.....	15
Figure 3 The Padano Veneto waterway system within the CNC of the TEN-T network	16
Figure 4 The Padano Veneto waterway system – zoomed view on the main IWW	16
Figure 5 River Po infrastructure managed by AIPO (in orange colour)	17
Figure 6 Fissero-Tartaro-Canalbianco-Po di Levante canal.....	18
Figure 7 Po-Brondolo canal.....	18
Figure 8 Distribution according to the NST 2007 categories of the freight traffic volumes on the Padano-Veneto IWW system in 2021.....	22
Figure 9 Historical series of transported tonnes and passengers in the 2013-2021 period.....	23
Figure 10 Actors with a direct contractual relationship in the Italian pilot case.....	28
Figure 11 Po River sections (or river reaches).....	32
Figure 12 Different relationships between stakeholders’ categories.....	37
Figure 13 Different relationships between stakeholders’ categories.....	37
Figure 14 Navigability conditions prediction model: execution plan	41
Figure 15 Smart bulletin: execution plan	41
Figure 16 Cold ironing: execution plan.....	42
Figure 17 GAP analysis: execution plan.....	44
Figure 18 SCMS – information collection for its customization to the Italian pilot scenario: execution plan	45
Figure 19 The set-up of acoustic emissions SHM measurements at Isola Serafini and Baricetta locks	46
Figure 20 The elements addressed by the Living Lab	48
Figure 21 Living lab invitation: I° LL cycle governance	50
Figure 22 Living labs: execution plan.....	51
Figure 23 Typical cold ironing structure and its main components.	59
Figure 23 Cold ironing and electric charging supply chain	60
Figure 24 Interventions in the Seine River axis	61
Figure 25 An example of the junction boxes developed in the pilot.....	63
Figure 26 Interventions in the Danube River	64
Figure 27 Breakdown in different categories of the fuel consumption at berths in the Fissero-Tartaro-Canalbianco waterway	70

Figure 28 Mapping of the landing places 71

Figure 29 Definition of the comprehensive strategic approach 72

Figure 30 Location of the interventions Fissero Tartaro Canalbianco Po di Levante waterway..... 79

Figure 31 Location of the interventions Po – Brondolo waterway 80